

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D8.3

Report on the conceptual design of the integrative tools

WP8 — T8.3

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
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Technical reference

Work package	WP 8 — Concepts and toolboxes
Task	T8.3 - Integrative models
Dissemination level ¹	PU = Public
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Contributing Participants	ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), VITO (BE), ISSeP (BE), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), NIVA (NO), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), NIC (SI), UU (SE), UOC (EL), UT (EE)
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D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 3

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Due date of deliverable	30 April 2023
Actual submission date	11 September 2023

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
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Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
1	06/06/2023	Denis Sarigiannis / AUTH Spyros Karakitsios / AUTH Hilko van der Voet / WR-BIOM Jasper Engel / WR-BIOM Johannes Kruisselbrink / WR-BIOM	Draft version for review
2	29/06/2023	Jean Lou Dorne / EFSA Matthias Herzler / BfR	Draft version with comments provided by reviewers
3	07/07/2023	Pascal Sanders / ANSES	Draft version with comments provided by the PARC Coordinator
4	04/09/2023	Hilko van der Voet / WR-BIOM Jasper Engel / WR-BIOM Johannes Kruisselbrink / WR-BIOM Denis Sarigiannis / AUTH Spyros Karakitsios / AUTH	Final version taking into account the comments from the reviewers and the PARC Coordinator

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D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 5

Abstract

PARC task 8.3 aims at integrating (PARC) data and models to support (integrated) exposure, hazard, risk and (health) impact assessment of chemical substances. In this deliverable a first blueprint of the model network is described, building on the idea of the open architecture paradigm in order to allow future models to be readily used within the same framework on the basis of a standardized input / output protocol. This document presents 1) an initial overview of user requirements for the model network, 2) a first conceptual design of the network, and 3) an inventory of models that are currently in view of the network, including links to other PARC activities. A bottom-up and top-down strategy is outlined for developing the model network. The top-down approach focuses on harmonized and general approaches for model interoperability and integration, e.g. based on semantic modelling approaches. The bottom-up approach focuses on establishing connections between specific modelling tools at a conceptual and technical level. This process focuses on specific needs and user requirements of e.g. PARC case studies. Promoting such (bilateral) connections between specific modelling tools will allow the PARC network to evolve over time. Also, it is deemed unfeasible to directly enforce common data standards and protocols on all modelling tools (and requiring them to adhere to them), due to their independent development processes as well as having in mind possibly diverse requirements of user groups such as scientists, regulatory risk assessors and other stakeholders. Following this strategy, initial case studies were started building on existing and new collaborations. These serve both as demonstrators and facilitators for model integration in the PARC integrative model network.

Key Words

Model network; Integrative risk assessment; Exposure; Hazard; Chemicals; Semantic design; Harmonisation; New approach methodologies; Physiologically-based kinetic models; Human biomonitoring

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 6

Contents

Document history	4
Abstract	5
1 Background	8
2 Approach in year 1 of PARC	10
3 Identification of user requirements	12
4 Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	15
4.1 Context and coverage.....	15
4.2 Categorisation of models and tools	17
4.3 Organisation and development of the network	20
4.4 Semantic design.....	22
4.5 Functional specifications of the model network	25
4.6 User interfaces	29
5 Current steps towards model network implementation	31
5.1 Inventory of models available in the PARC consortium	31
5.2 Overview of T8.3 partners and contributions	36
5.3 Established and potential links between models	44
5.4 Relation with other PARC projects.....	46
5.5 Critical analysis of the situation.....	54
6 Next steps towards model network implementation	55
6.1 General plan for operationalisation.....	55
6.2 Further identification of user requirements.....	55
6.3 Further elaboration of the overarching conceptual and technical design (top-down) 55	
6.4 Linking of models in the context of specific needs and user requirements following from (PARC) case studies (bottom-up)	56
7 PARC model network exit strategy	58
7.1 Exit strategy timeline	58
7.2 Evaluate the factors that impact an exit.....	58

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 7

7.3	Increase online presence and PPARC model network awareness.....	59
7.4	Communicate the exit strategy to developers, users, and stakeholders.....	60
7.5	Identify the legal and financial considerations during the exit process.....	60
8	<i>References</i>	61
9	<i>Annex: Models available within the PARC consortium to be included in the network.</i>	65
9.1	Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) toolbox.....	65
9.2	INTEGRA.....	69
9.3	VEGAHUB.....	72
9.4	STACKn.....	73
9.5	QsarDB.....	74
9.6	Specific PBK, systems biology model and AOPbot	76

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 8

1 Background

Realistic assessments of human health risks from chemicals are increasingly being supported by application of sophisticated mathematical and statistical modelling techniques. These have been developed by a wide range of parties. As a consequence, models and accompanying data sets have been implemented in different formats and software tools and are not available in one place. This hampers their accessibility and use by a wider community including regulatory assessors, scientists (modelers), and other stakeholders. In particular connecting or combining several models and data for an integrated examination accounting for all variabilities and uncertainties, for example to simultaneously consider several sources and routes of exposure, is often a cumbersome if not impossible process. The need for interoperability of data and models has been recognized by several scientific and regulatory processes, closely related to PARC (Ayris et al., 2016, Kruisselbrink et al., 2021, EFSA, 2021, de Jong et al., 2022, Cascio et al., 2022, Cappè et al., 2019, de Alba Aparicio et al., 2018, Eva et al., 2022, Knetsch and Ruether, 2016, Kosnik et al., 2022).

In the context of integrative modelling, **PARC** objective OO12 is to **develop models** and innovative concepts for risk assessment **and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake** (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023). PARC task 8.3 will develop a network or ecosystem of (linked) models and tools for integrated exposure, hazard, risk and (health) impact assessment of chemical substances. For this purpose, an overarching and harmonised framework will be developed to which models and data of PARC work packages 4 to 8 can be mapped to, which allows for specification of links between them and their implementation in a functional open infrastructure, i.e. the **PARC integrative model network** (PIMN). Models and data outside of PARC may be considered as well. The PARC integrative model network will also link to other PARC toolboxes such as the safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) toolbox that is being developed in task 8.1.

The PARC integrative model network should be of value to a wide range of user groups. The main stakeholders are regulators of chemical safety and risk assessors, primarily at the European and national levels. These stakeholders should have access to findable, accessible, interoperable and reproducible (FAIR) implementations of regulatory accepted modelling approaches for chemical risk assessment. Another important group of stakeholders consists of scientists who contribute to the advancement of effective

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 9

chemical risk assessment with innovative modelling approaches. These approaches may be based on new types of data (e.g. HBM, NAM, or biosystems data) and / or combinations of (existing) risk assessment models into new workflows or models (e.g. aggregate exposure, PBK, or systems biology models, or advanced statistical analysis methods). These user groups should profit from better accessibility of models and data and improved connections between them in an integrative network. The model network is also designed to allow transparent communication about new proposals for regulatory use between user groups, not only regulators/assessors and scientists, but also user groups from industry or NGOs.

This document presents the first version of the conceptual design of the network including its functional requirements and initial thoughts on the technical specifications for linking data and models. It is expected to evolve over time when it takes on board input from stakeholders. In particular PARC projects and case studies will initially drive the design of the model network. Therefore the document does not aim to provide a complete guidebook towards the development of the PARC integrative model network, but rather it seeks to foster discussion and exchange of ideas towards making final decisions among the project team and the involved stakeholders. To this aim this concept document will be circulated to the PARC stakeholder forum after its review by the Management Board to come to a stable version that will represent the final roadmap for the PARC integrative model network.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 10

2 Approach in year 1 of PARC

The PARC consortium covers science in over 200 institutes and therefore it is almost impossible to know the best models for inclusion in the network in advance. In addition, even with a relatively limited number of models, a significantly large number of model connections can potentially be established to support different user groups and modelling tasks. Therefore, it was decided that the initial PARC integrative model network will be established in a stepwise (bottom-up) fashion following from specific needs and user requirements of PARC case studies in WP 4-8. In addition, partially based on input from these case study examples, a top-down approach will be used to develop an overarching and harmonised framework (metamodel) for integration of models and data in the network.

In year 1 of PARC, we started to make an inventory of user requirements along two lines. First, initial steps were made to involve within-PARC stakeholders to sketch their specific requirements for a model network. An inter-WP task force has been created bringing together the co-leaders of WP4, 5, 6 and 8 to discuss scientific strategy alignments. In this regard, the within-PARC stakeholders have been asked for their input vis-à-vis user/stakeholder requirements for the PARC model network. In parallel, an inventory of models in view of PARC collaborations was started among Task 8.3 participants. In addition, an inventory of collaborations with other PARC projects that would fit the overall objective of implementing a functional open PARC modelling tool network was established. In these ways, it was ensured that activities in the model integration project were useful for aims of other PARC projects as well. Finally, conceptual ideas about integrative modelling and establishing connections between models and models and databases in the PARC integrative model network were established. These are summarised in the present document.

Initial case studies were started building on existing and new collaborations. These serve as demonstrators for model integration in the PARC integrative model network. In particular, a collaboration with the real-life mixtures project in subtask 6.2.3 was used to establish connections between HBM data and models in the integrative model network. This collaboration links PARC activities on HBM data organisation in WP 4, the development of risk models based on HBM data in WP 6, the FAIRification of HBM data in WP 7 and the PARC model network in WP 8. Data formats were developed to allow data controllers of specific HBM datasets to transfer quality controlled HBM data to the

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 11

Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) software (see Annex 9.1 for a description). Here, the MCRA toolbox represents multiple (integrated) models in the PARC integrative model network. MCRA functionality was upgraded to allow for analysis of HBM data, e.g. preprocessing of the HBM data with harmonised models, statistical modelling of the processed data for mixture selection, and a first version of (cumulative) risk assessment based on HBM data was implemented. PARC colleagues were trained on uploading and analysing HBM data and on using a generic PBK model in MCRA.

Within task 8.3 a collaboration was started between co-leads WR-BIOM and AUTH, focussing on the development of technical links between different models in the Integra and MCRA toolboxes. Integra, developed at AUTH, has extensive functionality to model non-dietary exposure. The MCRA toolbox, developed at WR-BIOM, has extensive functionality to model dietary exposure. In this case study, a conceptual link between relevant Integra and MCRA models will be established. In addition, a technical link will be established between them to allow use of dietary exposures from MCRA in Integra, and use of non-dietary exposures from Integra in MCRA. The conversion has to address possible differences in data formats and dictionaries, and it has to handle different options for accessing the model outputs, ranging from manual exchange via e.g. spreadsheet files to use of an application programming interface (API). The conversion functions will be placed in a shared location as a prototype for other future links between modelling tools in the PARC integrative model network.

Task 8.3 representatives participated in several cross-WP groups on structuring concepts, vocabularies and semantic modelling, mainly organised by WP 7 (FAIR data). These activities will lead to a conceptual model for the PARC model and data landscape, and ultimately to a PARC metamodel to describe all relevant entities for the risk assessment of chemicals. First investigations have been performed into the useability of existing ontologies and semantic artefacts for improving the interoperability within PARC between various models and data collections. These general activities were considered in the light of specific case studies, such as the case studies of the Real-life mixture project in task 6.2.3.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 12

3 Identification of user requirements

The PARC model network should support different user groups and modelling tasks for chemical risk assessment. As mentioned in section O, the user groups include not only regulatory risk assessors but also other interested stakeholders such as researchers (modelers), industry, and NGOs. In addition, the PARC model network should also consider endpoints for transparent reporting of the modelling results according to (regulatory) documentation requirements, to e.g. risk managers. It should be noted that the requirements for the PARC integrative model network may differ between user communities and are expected to vary over time according to changes, e.g., in public perception and governmental policies. Consequently, the model network should not only address current requirements, but should be designed in such a way that future user requirements can be accommodated as well, e.g. by integrating new models. The PARC model network should facilitate efforts for harmonization and alignment of the different scientific and regulatory communities and fields by 1) facilitating harmonization and alignment of the models and tools used and endorsed within and across the different communities, 2) providing common user interfaces or harmonized entry points in which tools and models come together in specific workflows to address specific scientific and/or regulatory research questions and offer dedicated reporting functionality for these.

User requirements are being collected from stakeholders within PARC in the first place. These stakeholders include model developers and users in most work packages of PARC.

Figure 1 schematically sketches the current relations with T8.3 and other projects and activities in PARC from which initial user requirements follow. It is anticipated that additional use requirements will be collected within PARC in collaboration with Task 2.2. In addition, other (selected) initiatives will be reviewed in which similar e-infrastructures are created, such as (EOSC-live, Open RiskNet, EPA CompTox dashboard or NICEATM's ICE platform).

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 13

Figure 1. Scheme showing the relations of the integrative model network with other tasks and projects in PARC

As an example, in the specific case study performed in collaboration with the Real-life mixtures project in task 6.2.3, the main user requirement of the PARC integrative model network is to have possibilities of using HBM data for mixture risk assessment. From this main requirement, other requirements follow:

- HBM mixture risk assessment results should be easily accessible and interpretable for risk managers and other regulatory stakeholders, and fulfil regulatory documentation needs
- Harmonized approaches for HBM mixture analysis, risk assessment and scenario analysis should be available in an easily accessible and open source toolbox with user interface
- The modelling toolbox should adhere to GDPR regulations and data protection requirements
- The modelling toolbox should support harmonized data collection and analysis to improve collaboration between research groups, risk assessors and regulators

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 14

- The toolbox should make use of advanced aggregate internal and external exposure models
- The toolbox should make use of PBK models for forward and reverse dosimetry both for exposure and hazard, for instance to translate external to internal guidance values or to translate HBM exposures in-between different biological matrices
- The toolbox should support risk assessment using different hazard and risk metrics including treatment of uncertainties
- The toolbox should support analyses of specific groups in the general or occupational population (e.g., age classes, workers of woman of child bearing age).

Other examples of research questions from which user requirements would follow could be:

- What is the risk of adverse effects in a national general population related to exposure from multiple media for a specific group of chemical substances, e.g. plasticizers?
- Can a new chemical substance be admitted to the market considering its possible health impacts and the existing background exposure to chemicals with the same health effects?
- What are the main chemical risks for a specific occupational group, e.g. painters?
- Can we quantify the relative risks of replacing or not replacing ingredient A with alternative ingredients B, C, D, etc. in a specific consumer product, e.g. a cosmetic product?
- In human biomonitoring programs, what limit values for which substances (or metabolites) and in which body fluid (e.g. urine, blood) should be used in correspondence with existing health-based guidance values?
- How are uncertainties due to insufficient knowledge or use of simplified models affecting answers to any of the questions above and which actions can be taken to reduce such uncertainties if needed?
- Is there a website where I can access useful models and data?

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 15

4 Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network

4.1 Context and coverage

The context of the PARC model network is the presence of many existing chemicals with potential health effects in the current world, and the need to regulate both existing and proposed new chemical substances (Figure 2). To support prospective and retrospective risk assessment of these chemicals, application of sophisticated mathematical and statistical modelling techniques is required. These methods should be available in easily accessible and transparent tools to support their uptake and (re-)use. The objective of task 8.3 in PARC is to develop a network or ecosystem that implements and links models, tools and data that are being developed and used in the Partnership in a harmonised way (see section 0). The model network should be able to address both regulatory and scientific needs (see section 3).

Figure 2. Context for the PARC model network.

In designing the PARC integrative model network it is realised that this is not a design from scratch. Many models and tools have already been developed and some of these have an established status in regulatory fields. Examples of such uses are ConsExpo

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 16

within REACH consumer exposure estimations, USEtox in UNEP's and SETAC's life cycle assessments and MCRA for EFSA's mixture risk assessment of pesticides. Consequently, the design of the PARC network will accommodate workflows that are developed in PARC by integrating existing models and tools, but will also include models and tools newly developed in PARC or (possibly) in other initiatives. This may include the development of new user interfaces if sufficient capacity is made available in PARC projects. The design will also make existing user interfaces better interoperable and create transparent workflows for integrated assessments using existing tools. The conceptual design has to recognise the limited budgets currently available in PARC task 8.3 for model and software development and will build on investments made by partners in other processes as well. Major characteristics of the PARC integrative model network will be transparency of models and calculations and, in collaboration with task 2.2, accessibility to workflows for regulatory risk assessments.

As shown schematically in Figure 3, the PARC integrative model network will need to cover a wide variety of regulatory and scientific fields. In a broad outline, it will be useful in addressing regulatory questions regarding:

- exposure assessment;
- hazard characterisation;
- risk assessment;
- health impact assessment;
- scenario analyses projecting possible consequences of risk management decisions.

Addressing these regulatory questions requires to bring together expertise from three different categories:

1. Models implementing knowledge from basic scientific fields, e.g.:
 - a. chemistry
 - b. systems biology, including omics, toxicokinetics
 - c. health sciences, including epidemiology and toxicology
 - d. demography
 - e. nutrition and behavioural sciences
 - f. environmental and agricultural sciences
2. Tools allowing inputs to vary according to practices and decisions on chemical uses made or proposed in the public or private sectors, e.g:
 - a. laws and regulations

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 17

- b. testing and new approach methodology
 - c. monitoring of exposure sources
 - d. human biomonitoring
 - e. life cycle impact assessment and chemical footprints
 - f. chemical substitution and alternatives assessment
3. Knowledge about modelling in view of uncertainties, and implementation is software, e.g.:
 - a. mathematics, statistics and modelling
 - b. uncertainty analysis across models and decision analysis
 - c. computer science

Figure 3. Regulatory fields (blue boxes) and related science fields (green boxes) in the scope of the PARC model network.

4.2 Categorisation of models and tools

The models that will be implemented in the PARC integrative model network may be categorised according to their role in the chain from environmental release of chemicals to (human and environmental) exposure and the resulting health, environmental and monetary risks and impacts. This is schematically depicted in Figure 4.

The figure schematically displays that a wide range of the modelling approaches are in scope of the PARC integrative model network. These range from multimedia environmental models to indoor air quality models and from exposure models capturing

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 18

the different exposure routes (inhalation, oral and dermal) to a suite of Physiologically Based Kinetic (PBK) models allowing the estimation of internal doses and hazards. Dose-response models will be included to derive hazard characterisations from available data. QSARs can be applied for predicting group membership toxicity, or physicochemical properties of compounds, as well as parameters necessary for the parametrisation of toxicokinetic models. Moreover, the model network will provide tools for advanced analysis applied to human and/or environmental monitoring data, identification of molecular and metabolic pathways, as well as articulation and quantification of AOPs.

Figure 4. Schematic view of linking the various data types (red boxes), model types (brown ovals) and additional methodologies (yellow ovals) across stages (green boxes) of the continuum from environmental release of chemicals to (human and environmental) exposure and the resulting health, environmental and monetary risks and impacts.

Based on Figure 4, the models that are currently in scope of the PARC integrative model network are broadly categorized as 1) environmental fate models, 2) exposure models, 3) PBK models, 4) systems biology models, 5) hazard characterisation models, 6) risk assessment models, 7) health impact assessment models and 8) economic models. In addition, uncertainty analysis approaches span all stages of the source to impact continuum. Table 1, presents an inventory and categorization of the models that are in

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 19

view of PARC collaborations. More details are provided in section 5. This rough categorization shows that this initial set of selected models span the source to impacts continuum of chemical substances. Refinement of the description and categorisation of models will take place while developing the overarching concept (metamodel) for the integrated model network.

Table 1. Categorisation of models/tools/contribution among task 8.3 participants, see Table 2 for additional details.

Category	Identified models/tools/contributions
Environmental fate models	USEtox (emission to impact), MCRA (food), VERMEER (food contact materials, cosmetics, environmental aquatic systems), STOP, INTEGRA
Exposure models	INTEGRA, MCRA, VERMEER, PBK interaction model IUSS, RLRS, mixture and aggregate models ANSES, USEtox
Biokinetic (PBK) models	INTEGRA, MCRA, VEGA, PBK interaction model IUSS, PBK models INERIS, QsarDB, PBK Model IISPV, STOP
Systems biology models	MCRA (AOP networks), quantitative AOPs UL-LACDR, PBK/SB model IISPV, INTEGRA
Hazard characterisation models	MCRA, VERMEER, ToxEraser, JANUS, VEGA, ToxRead and VERA, STACKn, PBK/SB model IISPV, QsarDB models, CPSign models
Risk assessment models	MCRA, VERMEER, RLRS, USEtox, STOP, INTEGRA
Health impact assessment models, Life cycle impact/ environmental footprinting models	USEtox, ToxEraser, INTEGRA LCA
Uncertainty analysis	INTEGRA, MCRA, PBK interaction model IUSS, PBK/SB model IISPV, USEtox (uncertainty on underlying factors), QsarDB, CPSign, STOP

As seen in Table 1 several modelling tools, such as INTEGRA, VEGA and MCRA, cover multiple categories and therefore may become integrated in a wide range of workflows that relate to Figure 4. These tools have a long development history and have secured long-term financing from multiple sources, including PARC. INTEGRA (Sarigiannis et al., 2016, Sarigiannis et al., 2022) has been under development since 2011 by PARC

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 20

partner AUTH (Greece) who is WP8 and T8.3 Co-leader, and its development has been supported by relevant projects, namely INTEGRA (CEFIC), HEALS (FP7), CROME (LIFE+), NEUROSOME, HBM4EU (H2020), as well as various contracts from industry for chemical risk assessment purposes. Continuous funding for maintenance has been ensured by the National Hellenic Research Foundation. VEGA (Benfenati et al., 2013) has been developed since 2011 by PARC partner IRFMN (Italy), and its development has been supported by various projects, including LIFESEEDIA, ToxBank, ORCHESTRA, EUTOXRISK, ANTARES, CAESAR, CALEIDOS, PROSIL, COMBASEm LIFEVERMER, CONCERTREACH, IN3 and the Italian Ministry of Health. MCRA is being developed since 1999 for the Dutch Institute of Public Health (RIVM) by PARC task 8.3 partner Biometris (Wageningen University & Research, WUR). Since 2015 MCRA is being developed in collaboration with EFSA towards a European platform for dietary mixture risk assessment of pesticides by member states (van Klaveren et al., 2023). The source code of MCRA open source and thus publicly available (Kruisselbrink et al., 2023b). An online, user-friendly, interface is also available (Kruisselbrink et al., 2023a).

4.3 Organisation and development of the network

The PARC model network is a digital ecosystem of interconnected tools, platforms, and services. Each of these tools has its own specific user community, its own user interface to serve its users, and its autonomous and independent development process under various governance structures. The aim of the PARC task 8.3 is to harmonize and link these tools in a network to support specific (PARC) regulatory and scientific questions, whilst pertaining the autonomy of their developers. For each task, different (combinations of) models in the network may be best for addressing it. Appropriate entry points (access) to (linked) models in them will be offered in collaboration with WP 2, for example via the PARCopedia initiative (Figure 5). Appropriate exit points of a workflow (reporting) may also eventually be needed. As mentioned in section 2, the network will initially be developed using a stepwise (bottom-up) approach focusing on workflows (links between) specific models and data that are required to support PARC case studies. In parallel, a top-down approach will be used to develop an overarching framework (metamodel) for integration of models and data in the network in a harmonized manner.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Krusselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 21

Figure 5. PARC model network and ontologies

The PARC integrative model network is not conceived as a single software solution under the control of a single party. Rather it consists of a digital ecosystem of models where each model has its own development team, process of development and / or governance structure. Each model or tool is considered to be a node in the network. Consequently, the PARC integrative model network will have a modular structure where each node or module represents a model or modeling tool/platform. This structure will enable the integration and application of specific combinations of models and data in workflows that are needed to support a specific data analysis task along the “full” source to impact continuum (Figure 4). Each module in the modular design represents a model or tool. Modules can be connected in different combinations (workflows) to support a wide range of data analysis tasks. This will support examinations such as aggregate exposure assessment focusing on environmental, consumer and occupational exposure, hazard characterization based on *in vivo*, *in vitro* and *in silico* approaches, and on risk assessments accounting for variability within human populations, and uncertainty of data and models.

Links between tools (nodes or modules) may already exist or may need to be developed based on user requirements (Figure 6). When establishing connections between

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 22

models, it is expected that a process of alignment of and harmonization between tools, and the data needed/produced by these tools, is needed. Given the independent development processes of the tools, it is reckoned that it is not feasible to enforce common data standards and protocols on all tools and requiring them to be updated accordingly. The stepwise (bottom-up) strategy by establishing bilateral connections between tools will allow the PARC network to grow in the course of time while avoiding this issue. By facilitating an increasing number of connections between tools, it is anticipated that global (top-down) harmonization of tools and data formats will naturally emerge within the model network. This harmonization is anticipated to emerge in the data (guided also by WP7), in the connection protocols, and by exploring semantic approaches for linking models (see next section 4.4).

Figure 6. Modules (ellipses) of the PARC model network in a digital ecosystem with evolving connections. Solid lines represent established links between modules, while dotted lines represent desired links. Modules from within and outside PARC and indicated in green and blue, respectively.

4.4 Semantic design

Models in the network will exchange information in the form of structured datasets and collaborations will be needed to ensure that model descriptions as well as datasets produced by one model are useful for linking to another model. Similar to the models covering a broad range of domains, also the data used/required by the models considered in the network is very broad and diverse. It includes, for instance, from (human) monitoring data, toxicological reference values and underlying dose-response data, dietary consumption data, use data of non-dietary products, data on chemical properties, etc. Models will typically have defined their own data formats, vocabularies and interpretations and more often than not, overlapping concepts will have different

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 23

meanings in different models, a situation referred to as semantic heterogeneity. Where established communities or networks under a single authority tend to define harmonised terms and data formats to avoid excessive technical overhead in data sharing efforts, this is not possible in a digital ecosystem without central control such as the PARC integrative model network.

A FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) data approach based on public ontologies and linked data technologies allows for otherwise unrelated project partners to annotate their datasets and models in a way that ensures interoperability and potentially machine actionability, no matter the model implementation choice or technicalities like the data exchange transport protocol.

In the first year of PARC, a cross-WP semantic working group has been established and the first domain specific initiatives have started, such as the 7.2.2 FAIR Human Biomonitoring Datasets project. The aim of these groups is to adopt or develop semantic models and provide technical guidance for easier integration of models and data from diverse stakeholders in PARC. The PARC integrative model network contributes to and aims to make use of these initiatives. Figure 7). The main areas of the task for developing a linked data ecosystem are, as illustrated in Figure 7, 1) development of broadly supported conceptual models/frameworks, 2) development of a persistence/storage infrastructure facilitating harmonized data (exchange) and ways of interfacing, 3) and development of dedicated (user) functionality/interfaces using the harmonized data ecosystem. The figure also sketches the roadmaps/steps for achieving the (final) goal of FAIR data, both in terms of the user functionality and the persistence infrastructure. The PARC model network is developed together with the linked data ecosystem, sharing the same conceptual model, and adopting the harmonized data infrastructure.

The transfer of HBM data was used as a first case study to elaborate connections between HBM data being made available by a data controller (DC) and models running on the MCRA software for risk assessment, by passing the datasets through a series of curation, quality control and conversion steps. The goal is to evolve this use case and make use of the semantic technologies and ontologies emerging from the PARC ecosystem and develop supporting tools until this dataflow fully leverages the FAIR capabilities of the platform, while maintaining the same level of usability for the end-user. The lessons learned and experience gained can then be put to use in FAIRification for other models and dealing with other types of data, e.g. environmental data. this will

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 24

avoid the need for time-consuming bilateral data and format conversions when integrating models.

Figure 7 Example of a methodology for creating and using conceptual models, deploying persistent infrastructure for semantic data and implementing end user functionality. The example was developed in the 7.2.2. project on integrating HBM data, but is broadly applicable and fits within a cross-domain goal of subsequently embedding the resulting ontologies and datasets in a linked data ecosystem.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 25

4.5 Functional specifications of the model network

The IT architecture of the PARC computational platform system will follow the open architecture paradigm in order to allow future models to be readily used within the same framework on the basis of a standardized input / output protocol. In this way, the tool will easily adapt to scientific / technical progress in the future.

Figure 8 Illustration of the landscape of modelling tools that need to be connected in the model network, visualized as a collection of tools implementing different models, implemented in different programming environments, and having their own user interfaces and user communities.

As mentioned in section 4.3, the basis of the functional design of the PARC model network is the premise that it is a network of independently developed modelling tools, each tool implementing its own specific models, each developed for its own (regulatory) purpose(s) and (user) community, etc. Figure 8 schematically illustrates this landscape as an unstructured collection of tools, and the aim of the modelling network is to establish connections and harmonization between these tools and combine them in specific workflows for addressing specific (regulatory risk assessment) questions. Figure 9 provides more detail for a particular modelling tool, representing a node in the network (Figure 6). In the design, a clear distinction is made between a model at the conceptual level and the particular software (tool) in which a model is implemented. For each individual modelling tool (a node in the network), the following assumptions are made:

- Each tool contains implementations of one or multiple models, and it may also be so that the same (conceptual) model is implemented in multiple tools.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 26

- Each tool implementing a model that needs input data from an external source provides its own specific format(s) required/supported for inputting this data. Input could be, for example, provided as one or multiple csv data files with some defined tabular structure, an excel data file with some defined structure, or it could be manually entered via a user interface.
- Similar to the inputs, each tool reports the results in its own specific way(s)/format(s) for presenting the outputs. This may be in the form of an html report displayed in the browser or, for instance, as csv files or other data files generated by the tool. For specific environments, such as R, results can also be outputted in the form of environment specific structures, e.g., R objects.
- Each tool has its own user community and provides its own user interface(s) / ways of interacting with the tool. For instance, some tools are published in the form of a website, providing the users of the tool the option to interact with the tool via the web browser. If, for instance, the tool is implemented in the form of an R package or a python package, then the models can be run via an R or python environment.
- Besides providing ways for user interaction, each tool may also facilitate automated interaction via one or multiple interfaces. Web applications may, for instance, provide web-services and a web API for communication with third party software (e.g., other tools in the network). R packages, for instance, may be linked in and used by other R packages or in analysis pipeline scripts developed in R.

Figure 9 Schematic example of a (conceptual) model implemented in a specific tool in a specific programming framework (.NET), with specific input formats (Excel, interactive user inputs), specific output formats (HTML), and specific options for interfacing (Web application, Web API). Conceptually, the model produces output x on input y.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 27

As mentioned earlier, given this landscape of models/tools the aim of the PARC model network is harmonization of models and tools to establish connections between them. This will allow for combining specific models and tools in pipelines or workflows dedicated to addressing specific (regulatory risk assessment) questions. The philosophy is that the whole of the digital ecosystem is greater than the sum of its parts. For each modelling task, a different combination of tools (workflow) in the network may be best for addressing it.

The concept of defining workflows of linked models and tools is illustrated in Figure 10. In establishing the modelling connections, we distinguish between connecting the models at the conceptual level and linking the tools at the technical level. At the conceptual level, there may be a desire to link the three depicted models. In this simple workflow, the results of the first model/tool serve as input for the second model/tool, which in turn is used for the third model. When establishing connections between models, this linkage at the conceptual level should, to a large extent, be clear. That is, before establishing technical connections, it should be clear for what modelling task this pipeline can be used and how the inputs/outputs are linked conceptually.

Figure 10 Scheme illustrating the linking of models in the model network. Top: conceptual linking of three models. Bottom, mapping and interfacing required for linking of the tools.

Given that the conceptual linking is clear and desirable, the tools should be connected at a technical level. Considering the diverse landscape depicted in Figure 8, this technical linking will often require tailored solutions for mapping the outputs produced by one tool to the inputs required by the next tool. Also, there is a choice of (user) interface for the model pipeline (series of connected models), which may be a separate manual pipeline in which the user uses the individual tools in sequence while collecting and mapping the inputs/outputs during the process. More advanced, this pipeline may be an automated pipeline, either presented in a new “workflow/pipeline tool”, which

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 28

could be a linking portal or dashboard or this pipeline could be integrated in one of the existing tools. The manual pipeline requires a way to export and input data obtained for and needed by the tools. The automated pipeline requires that the tools have interfaces for automated running of the models.

It should be noticed that in practice, the modelling workflows may become much more complex than the simple linear pipeline depicted in Figure 10, involving many more tools and models and possibly including parallel modelling steps.

At the technical level, for automated interfacing with the tools of the model network, we can distinguish two inherently different types of tools; tool presented as downloadable packages (e.g., R packages, python packages or applications written in C#/Java) and tools presented as web services, in which case the tool is installed on a remote web server, and the model can be run via a web connection. In the former case, interfacing possibilities are often specific for the programming language/environment in which the packages are developed. E.g., establishing an automated connection with an R package requires interaction via an R session. For web services, the WebAPI standard can be considered the de facto standard for automated linking.

Currently, containerisation is a popular approach for packaging tools in standalone and platform independent containers. These containers can be run in local constellations as well as constellations of (micro)services. Communication can be standardised via WebAPI standards. Figure 11 illustrates this concept for a tool implemented as an R package. Packaging tools in containers also facilitates building of modelling pipelines in platforms like the STACKn.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 29

Figure 11 Example of a tool, implemented in an R package wrapped in a container.

As mentioned, the technical possibilities to establish links between tools and for building (automated) analysis pipelines constituting of multiple tools much depends on the specific formats of the inputs/outputs and the possibilities for interfacing. The level in which a tool adheres to standardized formats can be coined the “level of interoperability”, which may be different for the data and the interfacing. The former is considered part of the semantic design and the work on data harmonization of WP7, which is also very relevant for the model network. Supporting standardisation for interfacing is a task specific for WP8.3.

The IT architecture of the PARC computational platform system will follow the open architecture paradigm in order to allow future models to be readily used within the same framework on the basis of a standardized input/output protocol. In this way, the tool will easily adapt to scientific and technical progress in the future. The open architecture should allow bottom-up initiatives to standardization for data and interfacing to be integrated in the network, while maintaining a top-down approach to achieve interoperability of models in a common framework.

4.6 User interfaces

The PARC model network will organise multiple workflows for users from different communities and with varying interests and levels of expertise in modelling (e.g. practical regulatory risk assessors vs. scientists). To ensure uptake of a workflow, a user-interface with dedicated reporting functionality will eventually be needed. These interfaces should allow for straightforward input of data and settings of the modelling tools involved in the workflow as well as transparent output integration and reporting according to (regulatory) documentation requirements. One possibility is to develop a

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 30

general user interface for all workflows. This would require harmonization of interfaces for different user communities, with possibly different interfacing needs for input and output. As an alternative, a catalogue may be developed comprising a limited number of flexible user interfaces dedicated to specific workflows covering different regulatory regimes and stakeholder requirements. These may be new interfaces, or extensions of an existing user-interface of a node in the network, which supports interoperability with other nodes. The catalogue of flexible user interfaces would be accessible from a central interface, e.g. PARCopedia, elixir, EOSC. Whether or not the use of flexible user interfaces is called for will be a matter of further discussion both internally within PARC and with the relevant regulatory and other stakeholders.

Nevertheless, the PARC integrative model network will be made accessible for the purposes of PARC by developing pipelines/workflows tailored to specific user groups. In addition, workflows could also be created to bridge the gaps between different (sub-) communities within PARC and therewith evolve and support further harmonization. User interfaces can be created for a workflow. The user interfaces will usually be web-based, but might in some cases be a client-side application, executed inside the web browser's window that will guide the user through the model network. Close collaboration and joint development with other tasks/projects within PARC is essential to establish workflows, especially considering the limited budgets currently available in PARC task 8.3

Another consideration is the e-infrastructure needed to train, integrate, and serve models and tools both within PARC and to the wider community. Within WP8 we will aim for vendor-agnostic and modern e-infrastructures (e.g. cloud computing and Kubernetes), and implement solutions as portable components that can be deployed in multiple settings (e.g. software containers) and with APIs and user interfaces that are primarily web-based.

For authentication and authorization, we will strive for all PARC systems to have a single-sign-on (SSO). To this end, we consider Life Science Login (formerly ELIXIR AAI) as the most viable solution.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 31

5 Current steps towards model network implementation

In this chapter, we first describe the status of the inventory of models. Secondly, we report on established or planned model connections and finally an overview of identified model collaborations within PARC is presented. These activities present a first view of the PARC model landscape and will be used to guide the development of the PARC integrative model network in year two.

5.1 Inventory of models available in the PARC consortium

A model inventory was started to evaluate the needs for coupling between models and databases. The model list (Table 2) is restricted to models and tools that are in view in PARC collaboration projects and focuses on their conceptual link to the source to impacts continuum (see Figure 4, section 4.2). In some cases, other PARC projects have already selected a subset of models for further use, in which case we refer to the selection process and list only selected models. Table 2 summarizes the models.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Krusselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 32

Table 2. Overview of models and tools that are currently considered for linking in the PARC integrative model network.

Model/tool	Environmental fate models	Exposure models	BioKinetic (PBK) models	Systems biology models	Hazard characterization models	Risk assessment models	Health impact models	Uncertainty analysis methods
INTEGRA (Sarigiannis et al., 2014) http://www.integra.cperi.certh.gr/	Multimedia concentrations including air (gases and particles), soil and water, in multiple scales, including and indoor air micro-environmental model	Multi-route, exposure reconstruction of HBM data	Life-stage dependent parameters, mother-fetus interaction, lactation exposure, life-long exposure, country specific anthropometric parameters	Under development		Probabilistic risk assessment (MCMC) Risk estimates per exposure route, aggregated risks	Links with CR functions	MCMC
MCRA (van Der Voet et al., 2020) https://mcra.rivm.nl/	Agricultural products to food, including agricultural use regulations and food processing	Multi-route, multi-substance, Probabilistic, acute and chronic, maximum cumulative ratio, compare model and HBM, mixture selection, clusters in the population	PBK models and factors, model instances per substance/population, forward and reverse, links to external PBK models	Health effects linked by AOP networks, effects representation by responses	Hazard characterisation based on in vivo, in vitro or in silico data and/or fitted dose-response models, includes assessment factor models	probabilistic cumulative aggregated risk, fixed or stochastic assessment factors, risk drivers		2-dimensional Monte Carlo, bootstrap, empirical and parametric distributions
VERMEER (Roncaglioni et al., 2022) https://www.vegahub.eu/portfolio-item/vermeer-cosmolife/	Food contact materials to food; cosmetics; aquatic environment	Oral, Dermal	Skin penetration		QSAR, prediction of effects	Margin of Safety for cosmetic ingredients or food contact materials		Chosen among several possibilities, probabilistic methods.
ToxEraser (Roncaglioni et al., 2022) https://www.vegahub.eu/portfolio-item/toxeraser-cosmetics/		The software is linked to VERMEER for the exposure			QSAR, suggested safer cosmetic ingredient		Replacement scenarios for cosmetics	

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Krusselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 33

Model/tool	Environmental fate models	Exposure models	BioKinetic (PBK) models	Systems biology models	Hazard characterization models	Risk assessment models	Health impact models	Uncertainty analysis methods
JANUS (Roncaglioni et al., 2022) https://www.vegahub.eu/janus-the-tools-for-prioritization-and-screening-of-chemical-substances-freely-available/					QSAR, prioritisation of substances. It can be used as predictive tool			The uncertainty of the prediction of multiple hazard model is assessed
VEGA (Roncaglioni et al., 2022) https://www.vegahub.eu/			QSAR, prediction of parameters		QSAR, prediction of effects			The uncertainty of each prediction is provided, based on applicability domain
ToxRead and VERA (Roncaglioni et al., 2022) https://www.vegahub.eu/portfolio-item/toxread/					Read-across tools based on similar substances			Uncertainty based on similarity among molecules and number of substances
PBK interaction model (IUSS)		Multi-route	Includes metabolic interaction					MCMC
STACKn / CPSign					QSAR via CPSign models but any containerized model can be served via API			Conformal Prediction (distribution-free uncertainty quantification)
PBK/SB model (IISPV) (Sharma et al., 2018, Rovira et al., 2019, Deepika et al., 2022)		Multi-route	All population (life stage model, 0-90 years), Pregnancy model, Forward and	y ROS Model (Neuro-, immune- and	In-vivo, In vitro omics-based predictions, in-silico (QSAR) data	Risk Assessment		P Biochemical uncertainty and physiological variability

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Krusselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 34

Model/tool	Environmental fate models	Exposure models	BioKinetic (PBK) models	Systems biology models	Hazard characterization models	Risk assessment models	Health impact models	Uncertainty analysis methods
			reverse, QSAR predictions of parameters	hepatotoxicity)				(Monte Carlo), MCMC simulations
RLRS		Multi-route, multi-substance, chronic deterministic				Risk characterisation		
Aggregation models (ANSES)		Multi-source, Multi-route, Multi-silo, chronic or acute						
SNMU/Clustering (ANSES) (Mancini et al., 2021)		Mixture selection, clusters in the population						No
Heavy metals mixture (ANSES)		Mixture, lifetime dietary exposure, PBPK						
HBM data tools (VITO) https://hbm.vito.be/tools European HBM dashboard https://hbm.vito.be/eu-hbm-dashboard PEH data Platform https://hbm.vito.be/peh-data-platform		HBM data pre-processing/harmonisation, data validation, data aggregation (summary stats)						
USEtox (Fantke et al., 2021) https://usetox.org/	yes	Deterministic, multimedia, multi-pathway exposure for different populations				Deterministic risk ratios	LCA, footprinting, substitution	Uncertainty ranges
PBK models (INERIS)			Generic and specific PBK models; multi-route exposure					

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Krusselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 35

Model/tool	Environmental fate models	Exposure models	BioKinetic (PBK) models	Systems biology models	Hazard characterization models	Risk assessment models	Health impact models	Uncertainty analysis methods
QsarDB models (UT) (Ruusmann et al., 2015) https://qsar.db.org/			QSAR prediction of parameters		QSAR prediction of effects			Uncertainty of predictions is based on applicability domain
PBK model (MU)		Mixture, lifetime dietary exposure, PBK for PFASs	Specific PBK model					Uncertainty analysis: sensitivity, specificity
QAOP models (UL-LACDR)				Under development				
STOP (NIVA) https://www.niva.no/en/source-to-outcome-predictor	yes	Environmental; multi-stressor, multi-source, multi-pathway (i.e. AEP), deterministic/probabilistic	Generic and specific PBPK models (fish)	AOP and qAOP informed	In vitro, in vivo, QSAR data used for effect modelling	Risk quotient, sum of Toxic Units (Concentration addition)	Under development	Under development

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 36

5.2 Overview of T8.3 partners and contributions

The partners of T8.3 offer 1) tool platform/software, 2) models, and/or 3) solutions for creating conceptual infrastructures or technical IT infrastructures. In addition, there are also partners contributing mainly to validation and testing of the model network via case studies. Table 3 shows a grouping of the PARC T8.3 partners on these four categories. Further details about the T8.3 participants and their initial contributions to the PARC integrative model network are presented below and in the Annex. Note that the partners below have been ordered according to their contribution to the project in terms of person months.

Table 3 Grouping of contributions of PARC T8.3 partners.

<u>Model platform / software provider</u>	<u>Model provider</u>	<u>Conceptual / IT infrastructure</u>	<u>Case study</u>
AUTH, WR-BIOM, IRFM, VITO, DTU, NIVA, UT	IRFM, MU, IUSS, IISPV, UOC, INERIS, UL-LACDR, WR-TOX	AUTH, WR-BIOM, UU, IISPV, ISSeP	AUTH, MU, Anses, NIC, SYKE, INSST, NMBU

AUTH: INTEGRA

In order to render INTEGRA interoperable with the rest of the model network, modifications will be done to integrate common input-output formats (entry points) that will be decided in T8.3 for the PARC model network, including necessary modules for adapting to the required spatial and temporal scale(s). In this sense, INTEGRA will be able to provide modelling services to the various parts of the source-to-effect continuum based on user needs, among other developed available modules in PARC network. This will be further facilitated by the translation of INTEGRA code into R and the delivery of modules. With regard to the modules of the source-to-dose continuum, INTEGRA will include the integration of material flow and life cycle analysis. Moreover, the developers of INTEGRA continue to evolve the link of internal dose estimates of parent compounds and metabolites with system biology models, towards systems biology-based AOPs.

WR-BIOM: MCRA

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 37

MCRA covers many models for exposure, hazard and risk. It already has a modular structure that will be optimised in relation to the PARC model network based on semantic models (cross-WP ontology working group, and specifically for HBM data link in 7.2.2). The link with HBM data is practically being developed in a collaboration with the Real-life mixture project (6.2.3; test version in October; functionality end Y1), where also multivariate data analysis models for mixtures are developed and implemented (functionality end Y1). An already integrated generic PBK model is being tested as part of 6.2.2 and 6.2.3, and the infrastructure is adapted to host PBK models that include metabolites of substances. Non-dietary exposure models (general population, occupational) will be linked to MCRA in the future to calculate aggregate exposure, and a functional design will be made as part of activity 6.2.1. MCRA includes quantitative uncertainty assessment, which is further assessed in collaboration with task 7.3.2 (scoping study in progress).

IRFMN: VEGAHUB

VEGAHUB includes a series of QSAR models, with emphasis on ensuring that the models generate transparent, understandable, reproducible and verifiable results. To achieve this, a series of tools has been optimised, which can relate the results obtained for the target chemical to the results obtained for similar (structurally related) compounds. VEGAHUB tools also provide reproducible approaches for read across, which is a tool to extract the required values for the target compound on the basis of the known values for similar substances. Overall, VEGAHUB will be able to contribute to the hazard identification aspects with QSARs pertinent to early biological effects and specific health outcomes, providing toxicity estimates that can be used for risk assessment purposes. With regard to multimedia environmental modelling, Vermeer Solvents and Oil will contribute to surface waters contamination estimation, while the phys-chem module of VEGA will contribute to multi-media modelling parameterization (compound specific parameters). With regard to exposure modelling, Vermeer FCM will contribute to dietary exposure assessment through the contribution of food contact materials. Regarding toxicokinetics, VEGA will further contribute to the parameterization of the PBTK models (kinetics and tissue:blood partition coefficients).

MU: PBK models for uncertainty in PFAS exposure

MU prepares a case study under T7.3.2 called Assessment of uncertainty in PBK models of PFAS exposure of humans and reverse dosimetry (short name: Uncertainty in PFAS

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 38

exposure). The study consists of the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) implementation of PBK models for PFAS exposure selected or developed in collaboration with partners from T6.2.3. And development for methodology for uncertainty analysis of such models that will be included in the model network.

As a first step, MU will prepare a review of available exposure data relevant to specific countries for which biomonitoring data are available (focusing on diet, including drinking water, consumer product exposures, and indoor environments). The study will utilize data from the previous project HBM4EU (T4.1.4.2 PARC project DataAnalysisHBM4EU) on teenagers. Later data on pregnant women will be used in collaboration with the PFAS and immunotoxicity case study (T6.2.3).

Parametrization of the PFAS model is expected to be done in collaboration with partners from T6.2.2 and T6.2.3, for unknown parameters QSAR models are being considered. Calculation of uncertainties in input data, model parameters (e.g. partition coefficients, physiological parameters, intrinsic human elimination half-lives) and global and local sensitivity of the model and its variables will be run in collaboration with partners from T7.3.2.

Finally, the model will be used for a reverse dosimetry to enable a comparison of estimated daily intakes calculated from external exposure with estimated daily intakes from internal exposure (measured PFAS blood concentrations).

IUSS PBK and systems biology models

IUSS modelling efforts will contribute to the translation of multi-route exposure into internal estimates, with a particular focus on the assessment of interactions at the level of metabolism. This is particularly important in combination with the work on AOP networks, which is another part of the work that IUSS will contribute. IUSS will develop routines for linking -omics data with qAOPs, towards the development of methodologies for incorporating NAMs in the risk assessment process.

UU: STACKn and CPSign

UU will contribute with the STACKn framework, equipped with LSLogin for Single-sign-on, and contribute to exploring model inventory, deployment and interoperability. UU will also contribute SAR models trained using CPSign equipped with distribution-free uncertainty quantification. UU will also contribute to evaluations of federated learning when this will occur.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 39

IISPV Aggregate exposure, PBK and system biology models

IISPV will contribute models for exposure assessment for multiple population groups towards public health risk assessment. IISPV will also have a particular contribution in internal dose models that address in detail the blood-brain-barrier, hippocampus and cortex toxicity, while they are also connected with systems biology models for neuro-, immune- and hepatotoxicity. Systems biology models are also applicable to ageing and particular diseases like Parkinson. It is freely available on FAIRDOM for users. The PBK model is being used for T6.2.2 and 6.2.3 for PFAS modeling and 5.3.4 for specific PBK models.

IISPV contributions related to model harmonization and uncertainty

IISPV is task leader for Task 7.3 Innovative analyses and will contribute to Task 8.3 based on experience with ontologies and uncertainty modelling, and based on experience with their exposure, PBK and systems biology models. IISPV is also creating a platform for text mining where networks can be generated based on keywords. This can be helpful for the development of AOPs and IATAs linking task 7.3 with 5.3 and 6.1. For the conceptual design of the PARC model network, IISPV contributes with knowledge about ontologies in the cross-WP Ontology working group. A scoping study is performed to overview the role of uncertainty analysis in human health risk assessment.

UOC: RLRS

The Real-Life Risk Simulation (RLRS) model developed by UOC aims at linking the low doses of multi-route long term exposures from multiple chemicals with hazard estimates, to predict the long-term risks for human health. The model will be developed as a stand-alone software within the next years and will be part of the exposure component of the model network, receiving input from both the multimedia model, as well as other parameters for modelling inhalation, dermal exposure and oral (dietary/non-dietary) exposure, delivering cumulative risks for real-life mixtures.

ANSES aggregate, data analysis and PBK models

ANSES develops several types of models, mostly in R and Rshiny. Aggregate exposure models, multivariate data analysis models and PBK models are expected to fit well with the PARC model network. Aggregate exposure models link occupational and general life exposures over multiple pathways; ANSES leads subtask T6.2.1 where European

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 40

exposure models will be linked to the PARC model network for aggregation. ANSES has also developed multivariate data analysis models in R for selection of chemical mixtures, which have been adapted and implemented in MCRA in the context of their co-leading the project T6.2.3 with RIVM. ANSES also has PBK models for metals for example that will be linked to MCRA. More generally, ANSES as co-leader of the T6.2 where several exposure, risk and health impact models will be developed will participate to the building of the PARC model network.

ISSeP

ISSeP will contribute to the provision of the GIS data interface for environmental exposure in the model network.

NIC contribution

NIC will contribute to the model network validation and more in particular to the validation of the multimedia environmental model

UL-LACDR AOP models

UL-LACDR is co-leading the activities in Task 5.3 and 6.1 that involve development of AOPs and the IATA system. In this sense, UL-LACDR will contribute to the organization of the toxicological information. Moreover, UL-LACDR will develop systems biology-based qAOP models. This will allow the assimilation and the translation of various data that will come from NAMs approaches (such as transcriptomics from in vitro systems). These models can be combined with PBK models (developed in other PARC tasks), and thus contribute to hazard metrics relevant for risk assessment.

VITO: HBM data tools/platforms

VITO has knowledge about integrated platforms and cross-cutting issues. VITO can contribute to the model network mostly by providing links to the data, for which they have a primary responsibility, in general (WP 7 co-lead) and specifically for HBM data (T4.1). VITO will contribute to Task 8.3 formally from year 2, but in practice intensive collaboration has already started in connection with Task 7.2 (FAIR data, specifically HBM data, semantic modelling and ontologies) and activity 6.2.3 (Real-life mixtures project). VITO is responsible for organising HBM datasets in PARC. VITO developed tools for data harmonisation of HBM data (data formats), data validation and data aggregation (<https://hbm.vito.be/tools>). Aggregated HBM data are integrated in the

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 41

European HBM dashboard (<https://hbm.vito.be/eu-hbm-dashboard>). VITO has developed the Personal Exposure and Health (PEH Data Platform) hosting individual HBM data from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies and Mom-study (<https://hbm.vito.be/peh-data-platform>), which will be further expanded with additional HBM data in PARC. WR-BIOM and VITO collaborated to create a data link between PARC HBM data and MCRA as part of the model network. Work is ongoing on ontology-based model harmonization, where VITO contributes with expert knowledge. In addition, VITO contributes with knowledge about aggregate exposure models from previous projects, in collaboration with activity 6.2.1, such as models identified by the ‘Source to dose’ project, such as EUSES, ConsExpo, MerlinExpo, S-Risk, etc.

DTU: USEtox

A leaflet introducing chemical risk and impact assessment metrics, model structure, outputs and interfaces of the UNEP/SETAC global scientific consensus model USEtox (<https://usetox.org>) will be introduced as well as a web-based user manual, introducing interfaces in more detail related to assessing chemicals in different consumer product applications, such as building materials, food contact materials, and personal care products, all falling under and being relevant for different European chemicals management legislations. USEtox will moreover be adapted further to be fully applicable in the European Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) and Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) frameworks. It is foreseen that these activities are executed as internal contributions to PARC from the USEtox International Centre. In addition, USEtox will be transformed to a web-based, modular and open-source software (start 2023), while its input/output will be linked with a relational database.

WU-TOX models

WU-TOX will contribute case studies using their PBK models, reverse dosimetry and QIVIVE models.

NIVA: STOP

NIVA’s Computational Toxicology Program (NCTP) has developed the Source-To-Outcome-Predictor (STOP) a graphical user interface (GUI) that combines exposure data from aggregate exposure pathways (AEP) with effect data from adverse outcome pathways (AOP) to yield risk predictions for single and multiple stressors (chemicals and

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 42

non-chemical stressors). The STOP-GUI and supporting databases such as NIVA's Risk Assessment database (RAdb) and standalone integrative analysis is mainly developed for environmental impact predictions, but principles and approaches may have utility also for non-environmental applications, although such efforts have not yet been assessed or undertaken. NIVA can contribute to the network by FAIRification of data repositories, development of ontology and controlled vocabularies, semantic modelling, development and implementation of AEP- and AOP-linked approaches in environmental impact assessment.

SYKE contributions

SYKE will contribute to the model network validation and, in particular, to the validation of the multi-media environmental model.

INERIS PBK models

INERIS has developed several PBK models for persistent and rapidly metabolized compounds that address particular life stages such as pregnancy and internal exposure of the developing fetus. INERIS also co-leads the 6.2.2 activity on lifelong exposure as well as the modelling working group of 6.2.3 Real-life mixtures, and will also streamline the development of PBK models towards the interoperability within the model network. At the same time, since INERIS is the developer of the PBK model of MCRA, they will continue working in the further development of the respective module and its adaptation to PARC model network needs, with a particular focus on HBM analysis.

INSST

INSST will contribute to the model network validation and, in particular, to the validation of occupational exposure models

NMBU (Norwegian University of Life Sciences)

NMBU will contribute to the model network validation and, in particular, to the validation of the internal exposure and early biological responses models.

UT: QsarDB

QsarDB.org (repository of models) includes information over 500 in silico predictive models grouped into six major groups: PhysChem properties, Environmental fate, Ecotoxic effects, Human Health, Toxicokinetics & Other. In this sense the QsarDB.org

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 43

will provide and receive input (interoperable with PARC Model Network) across various points of the source-to-effect continuum, with a particular focus on the prediction of toxic potency regarding health endpoints that are relevant for risk assessment purposes. Aiming at a high level of interoperability with the PARC Model network, QsarDB developers will contribute also to the ontology group.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 44

5.3 Established and potential links between models

In the first year of PARC several concrete examples of model integration were established. Roughly the activities focused on integration of HBM analysis models, mixture analysis models, aggregate exposure models, and kinetic models in the PARC model network.

WR-BIOM and VITO, in collaboration with RIVM, established a link between HBM data and tools developed by VITO for the purpose of quality control of EU HBM data and the MCRA toolbox for risk assessment. Data formats were developed that HBM data managers will use to upload data to MCRA. In MCRA, data conversion routines were established to convert these data into the internal (relational) data formats of MCRA human monitoring data. Data preprocessing in the MCRA module for human monitoring analysis was adapted to reflect the harmonised methods proposed in HBM4EU and PARC.

WR-BIOM, ANSES and UU-IRAS harmonised ANSES R and MCRA models regarding mixture selection and implementation of the methods developed in previous projects in the MCRA toolbox. These methods include SNMU, additional cluster analysis of individuals connected to the selected mixtures and graphical network analysis. The user interface and output organisation of the MCRA module Exposure mixtures was developed according to the needs of the Real-life mixtures project in task 6.2.3.

WR-BIOM, ANSES and RIVM developed better model connections between HBM data and risk assessment models. The functionality of the MCRA module for risks was extended by allowing preprocessed HBM data as input for internal exposures in a specified biological matrix. An illustration of the mentioned collaborations is shown in Figure 12.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Krusselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 45

Figure 12. Examples of collaboration between PARC tasks and projects.

WR-BIOM and RIVM implemented a specific PBK model developed at RIVM describing chlorpyrifos and two metabolites in the MCRA toolbox. This will serve as an example of how to model metabolites for other PBK models that include metabolites.

WR-BIOM and AUTH have started to develop model links between MCRA modules and Integra. This should allow to transfer dietary exposures modelled in MCRA to Integra, and to transfer non-dietary exposures modelled in Integra to MCRA. R data conversion scripts will be developed in a shared github repository.

AUTH (with INTEGRA) and WR-BIOM (with MCRA) work on the source-to-dose models (dietary and others) may be used to estimate external exposure which could then serve as an input of PBK models to estimate the internal exposure. Concentrations of biologically effective doses, computed using PBK models (AUTH with INTEGRA INERIS and IISPV with PBK models), may be used as an input for real-life mixture analysis (relative potency factors/RPFs, hazard indices/HIs, etc.). Moreover, such concentrations of biologically effective doses as predicted by PBK models can be combined with qAOP models for hazard prediction.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 46

5.4 Relation with other PARC projects

PARC covers science in over 200 institutions. For constructing a conceptual design of a PARC model network, two approaches were followed. Within-PARC stakeholders were invited to sketch their specific requirements for a model network first. In parallel, Task 8.3 participants made an inventory of collaborations with other PARC projects that would fit the overall objective of implementing a functional open PARC modelling tool network. In this way, activities in this project were useful for aims of other PARC projects as well. Finally, the conceptual ideas about useful integrative models and their connections with each other and with databases were summarised in a draft conceptual design for the PARC model network. Missing parts were also identified to guide upcoming projects.

An inventory of collaborations was started that could feed the development of the PARC model network. An inventory of existing and desirable collaborations is shown in Table 4. Further description of these collaborations is given below the table.

Table 4. Inventory of T8.3 collaborations

#	PARC WP/Task/Activity/Project	Partners involved (proposed 8.3 lead in bold)	Description
1	8.3, 2.2	AUTH , WR-BIOM, ...	Report on user requirements (milestone 8.3), foreseen links to PARCopedia
2	7.2, 8.3, 7.3, 9.2	VITO , WR-BIOM, AUTH, MU, IISPV, DTU, UT, NIVA, ...	Cross-WP group semantics and data exchange formats
3	8.3, 4.1, 6.2.3, 7.2.2	WR-BIOM , VITO, ANSES, JSI, UU ...	Link HBM data (e.g. HBM4EU) and analysis models to MCRA using HBM ontology
4	8.3, 6.2.3	WR-BIOM , RIVM, VITO, ANSES,...	Compare HBM data to modelled exposures in MCRA
5	8.3, 6.2.3	WR-BIOM , ANSES, UU-IRAS, IRFMN, ...	Implement models for mixture selection and risk assessment in MCRA
6	8.3, 6.2.1	WR-BIOM , ANSES, Unisante, RIVM, TTL, NIVA	Functional design for model connections Aggregate exposures from different sources and routes for general population and workers
7	6.2.2, 8.3	INERIS , AUTH, WR-BIOM, IISPV, IUSS, ANSES, WR-WFSR, WU-TOX, ...	Refinement or development of PBK models for RA

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 47

8	8.3, 6.2.3	WR-BIOM , INERIS, AUTH, IISPV, RIVM, ANSES, MU, ...	Implement updated PBK models for Real-life mixtures RA in MCRA
9	8.3, 6.2, 5.3	WR-BIOM , RIVM, ANSES, ...	Implement non-dietary exposure and dose-response models for integrated RA in MCRA
10	7.3.2, 8.3	IISPV , WR-BIOM, ANSES, VITO, UU, NIVA, ...	Scoping study uncertainty of data and models
11	6.2.3	WR-BIOM , ANSES, RIVM, VITO, IRFMN, ...	Implement risk assessment with HBM in MCRA
12	6.2.3	VITO , UU-IRAS, WR-BIOM, FHI	Epidemiological dose – effect relations: linking mixture exposures to health effects
13	6.2.4	VITO , UU-IRAS, WR-BIOM, ANSES...	Health impact - methods
14	6.2.4, 8.3	VITO , UU-IRAS, WR-BIOM, DTU, ANSES, ...	Health impact - indicators
15	8.3, 7.2.3, 5.3	AUTH , IUSS, NIVA, ...	Case study bisphenols
16	6.2.1, 6.2.3, 8.3	ANSES , RIVM, VITO, WR-BIOM, ...	Case study metals : aggregate exposure, mixture risk assessment and health impact.
17	7.3.2, 4.1.4.2, 6.2.2, 6.2.3., 7.3.2, 8.3	MU , IISPV, WR-BIOM, ANSES, VITO, RIVM, ...	Case study: Assessment of uncertainty in PBK models of PFAS exposure in humans and reverse dosimetry (uncertainty in PFAS exposure)
18	8.1, 8.3	AUTH , DTU, ...	Life cycle analysis
19	8.3	IRFMN , UT, ...	Integrate in-silico tools (VEGAHUB, QSARDB) in PARC model network
20	8.3	IISPV , UL-LACDR, IUSS, NIVA...	Integrate AOP networks in PARC model network
21	8.3, 5.1.	NIVA , ISSeP, ...	AEP- and AOP-informed cumulative risk assessment of environmental exposure scenarios (agricultural, industrial, riverine and Arctic exposure scenarios)
22	6.2.1, 6.2.3, 8.3	TTL , ANSES,...	Case study occupational
23	8.3	UU , ...	Case study use of STACKN platform for deployment of example services
24	8.3	AUTH , ...	Convert Integra code to R, make modular and open source
25	8.3	UOC , ...	Link extended real-life risk simulation model to multiple sources and specific populations to PARC model network
26	5.3, 6.1	AUTH , IISPV, UL-LACDR	QIVIVE, AOPs, qAOP and IATA for risk assessment purposes
27	6.2.2	AUTH , INERIS, IISPV, ANSES	PBK models for lifelong exposure

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 48

28	8.2	AUTH , NKUA, UMU, SLU, IRFMN	Early Warning System for chemical risks
29	8.1	AUTH , RIVM, EMPA, UNINA, IRFMN	SSbD computational tool
30	6.4.2	UT , UG-PL, IRFM, UNIBASEL, NIPH(VKM), ISS, INERIS, UKCHE, NIVA, EA	Readiness of ML and AI QSAR NAMs for chemicals NGRA
31	8.3, 6.2.2	WR-BIOM , AUTH , INERIS, MU	Linking MCRA, Integra and PBK models

In more detail, the collaborations are described as follows:

1) Report on user requirements (milestone 8.3), foreseen links to PARCopedia

User requirements have been defined by extensive consultation with various user groups within the consortium, as well as from experience of the key model network developers with the regulatory arena. At the same time, AUTH is also responsible for the computational development of PARCopedia, ensuring the close link of the model network. As mentioned above, PARCopedia may host an entry point for the (interface to) the workflows that are developed in the model network.

2) Cross-WP group semantics and data exchange formats

PARC Task 7.2 initiated different cross-WP groups that aim to increase availability, reuse and exchange of data using semantic technologies and a FAIR methodology. This includes both a bottom-up approach, where Task 8.3 will contribute use cases to and adopt domain specific results and implementations from these groups and top-down guidance that will provide the semantic compatibility layer needed to combine datasets and models from different domains, where Task 8.3 will be providing input for the metamodel and test it out in practice.

3) Link HBM data (e.g. HBM4EU) and analysis models to MCRA using HBM ontology

In collaboration with PARC project P6.2.3_Y1_RealLifeMixtures ‘New risk assessment and exposome methodologies to reduce exposure and risk of real-life mixtures’, the MCRA platform developed by WR-BIOM for RIVM was introduced as a computational platform to link human biomonitoring (HBM) data from PARC to models for mixture analysis and comparison with modelled exposures. In collaboration with PARC projects P.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets ‘FAIR

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 49

and sustainable storage of human biomonitoring (HBM) datasets’, a start has been made for FAIR data organisation of HBM data, with an eye on their use in the PARC model network. Trainings on the use of MCRA for mixture analysis were given online and at a project meeting in Athens in November 2022. See example in 5.3.

4) Compare HBM data to modelled exposures in MCRA

The existing MCRA functionality to model internal exposure is used for a comparison of modelled and observed (HBM) exposure, as part of the envisioned IRA Dashboard. If there is sufficient similarity, modelling can be used to identify the sources and pathways that contribute most to the exposure, i.e. the potential risk drivers. See example in 5.3.

5) Implement models for mixture selection and risk assessment in MCRA

Methods on mixture selection and risk assessment available from previous projects (EuroMix, HBM4EU) were implemented in MCRA and optimised for further use. A statistical expert group was started to enlarge the proposed options to perform mixture risk assessment. Trainings on the use of MCRA for mixture analysis were given online and at a project meeting in Athens in November 2022. See example in 5.3.

6) Functional design for model connections regarding aggregate exposures from different sources and routes for general population and workers

In collaboration with PARC project P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate ‘Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures’, from a large inventory, relevant models and tools for assessing exposure from various sources will be selected to develop a functional design on the inclusion of these models in the PARC model network, and more specifically on their link to MCRA. As an example of this work, the connection between the PACEM and ConsExpo models of RIVM and MCRA, was started.

7) Refinement or development of PBK models for RA

In collaboration with PARC project P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk ‘Refinement and development of PBPk models for human risk assessment’, the needs to include PBK models in the PARC model network are described. For several categories of substances, specific PBK models are being compared to the generic EuroMix PBK model which is already part of MCRA.

8) Implement updated PBK models for Real-life mixtures RA in MCRA

Needs in the real-life mixture project will lead to setting implementation priorities for PBK models.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 50

9) Implement non-dietary exposure and dose-response models for integrated RA in MCRA

Models selected in PARC project P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate ‘Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures’ will be linked to MCRA to allow for the computation of predicted aggregated exposure using agreed models.

10) Scoping study uncertainty of data and models

In collaboration with Task 7.3, concepts and data structures to integrate uncertainty modelling in the PARC model network are set up. As a first step, a scoping study is performed.

11) Implement risk assessment with HBM in MCRA

In collaboration with the 6.2.3 Real-life mixtures project, the models for mixture risk assessment using internal exposure are discussed and updated, and will be recognisable as the MCRA Integrated Risk Assessment (IRA) Dashboard.

12) Epidemiological dose — effect relations

In collaboration with the 6.2.3 Real-life mixtures project, models linking mixture exposures to health effects will be considered for inclusion in the integrative model network.

13) Health impact — methods

In collaboration with PARC project P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod ‘Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies’, first step have been taken to identify methods for health impact assessment (HIA) based on epidemiological studies. These methods should be connected to the overall PARC model network.

14) Health impact — indicators

In collaboration with PARC project P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’, first steps have been taken to identify indicators for health impact assessment (HIA) based on epidemiological studies. These indicators should be connected to the overall PARC model network.

15) Case study bisphenols

As a starting point, the bisphenols case study will set up a comprehensive workflow for multiple compounds making use of existing tools like modules of INTEGRA, MCRA, USEtox, VEGA HUB, ConsExpo, and PACEM in an interoperable network, while identifying new functionalities that have to be implemented and integrated in the model network. Overall, this project will contribute to the development, testing and integration of interoperable tools for innovative models. These models will be developed and validated for further

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 51

activities, by implementing AOP-based and benchmark dose (BMD) models applied to NAM data in hazard assessment, integrated external and internal exposure assessment towards refined risk assessment. This will be carried out by integrating models related to near and far field exposure modelling, reconstruction of HBM data, internal exposure assessment accounting for co-exposure interaction and QIVIVE for introducing NAMs in the risk assessment process. The key deliverable of the specific project **will be the alpha version of the conceptual design of the PARC model network**. Towards this aim, early versions of web-based software will be delivered to demonstrate and test the applicability and overall performance of the model network on the functional connection of different data types and addressing data gaps with computational methods to support risk assessment. Case studies will demonstrate how data across the source-to-effect continuum are interconnected in both directions (from source to effect and vice versa), and at the same time will facilitate the design of the model network. Experience from this project will feed into future requirements of the model network itself, as well as to its access points.

16) Case study metals

In T6.2, metals are part of the different projects included in this task to develop integrative risk assessment. Thus, aggregate exposure, PBK model including long term exposure, mixture risk assessment and health impact will be performed using PARC model network for this chemical family considering general life and occupational exposures. Thus metals can be used as a relevant case study for the implementation of the integrative risk assessment approach in PARC model network.

17) Uncertainty in PFAS exposure

MU is preparing a case study in close connection with T7.3 Innovative analysis. Using PBK models implemented in MCRA, HBM data will be used together with model parametrization for different PFAS congeners to assess an uncertainty in PBK modeling and reverse dosimetry. The case study will be done in collaboration with activities 4.1.4.2, 6.2.2, 6.2.3 and 7.3.2.

18) Life cycle analysis

LCA models will be included in the model network, facilitating the analysis of exposure to chemicals through their entire life-cycle, as well as to calculate the environmental footprint of chemicals and materials production; this is of key importance in the SSbD assessment.

19) Integrate in-silico tools (VEGAHUB, QSARDB) in PARC model network

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 52

Various in silico tools for predictive toxicology will be linked through the PARC model network, increasing its capacity for risk assessment, as well as for the needs of SSbD assessment and the EWS.

20) Integrate AOP networks in PARC model network

AOPs represent a very promising method for integrating toxicological information from various species and test batteries, towards a description of the mechanisms behind adverse outcomes. Inclusion of AOP networks within the PARC model network is critical for the mechanistic interpretation of the tox data that will come from WP5 for use in the regulatory context.

21) AEP- and AOP-informed cumulative risk assessment of environmental exposure scenarios

NIVA are involved in developing and using NAMs for bisphenols (T5.1.2), develop AOPs for endocrine disruption (T5.3.2), assess the impact of plant protection products (T6.4.4), combined toxicity and cumulative risk of complex mixtures (T6.4.1) and development of FAIR-compliant approaches and integrative models (T7.1, T7.2, T7.3) that will be used to support development of models in WP8.3 and specifically integrate environmental case studies into the PARC modelling framework.

22) Case study occupational

Occupational case study in collaboration with the PARC T6.2.1 and T6.2.3 that will be involved in developing a set of Integrative models.

23) Case study use of STACKN platform for deployment of example services

Examples of AI models will be deployed and served via STACKN to explore the interoperability within PARC.

24) Convert Integra code to R, make modular and open source

Within PARC, INTEGRA code (which is now developed in AcslX) will be translated into R. This will facilitate its link with the other modules of the PARC model network, as well as its further dynamic link with systems biology models.

25) Link extended real-life risk simulation model to multiple sources and specific populations to PARC model network

The PARC model network will be benefited by the work done by the group of UoC regarding the real-life risk simulation model, providing additional tools for risk assessment of chemical mixtures, that rely on real-life mixtures obtained from HBM studies.

26) AOPs and IATA for risk assessment purposes

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 53

Systems biology-based AOP models developed in Task 5.3 and Task 6.1 will be developed by integrating the most relevant profiling and phenotypic data generated in relation to external exposure and health observations. Models will be linked to PBK models, to bridge external and internal exposure, and will be parameterized using omics data, both from (iteratively generated) in vitro, as well as human cohort data. The final systems biology model will be used to predict risk for individual subjects, using a population (multilevel) approach. An Integrated Approach to Testing and Assessment (IATA) as proposed by OECD will be developed in order to make the most efficient use of all available data and converge towards an integrated testing strategy (ITS) that couples advanced bioinformatics and computational analysis of toxicological and biomonitoring data to targeted testing assays. In this sense, very strong links are expected with WP5 and WP6.

27) PBK models for lifelong exposure

PBK models hold a key role within the emission to effect continuum, and they are key components of both in vitro to in vivo extrapolation (as well as to reverse QIVIVE), and for assimilation of HBM data, through exposure reconstruction. In this sense, linking the lifelong exposure PBK models developed in Activity 6.2.2 within the PARC model network, will expand its applicability domain with regard to the respective policy questions to be addressed.

28) Early Warning System for chemical risks

EWS computational platform relies on the assimilation of multiples lines of evidence and interpretation of heterogenous data streams. In this sense, the EWS will benefit from the inclusive and modular design of the PARC model network that will provide the mechanistic link and interpretation of the various monitoring tools such as environmental and human biomonitoring data.

29) SSbD computational tool

The SSbD toolbox to be developed in Task 8.1 will make use of the available tools for safety (mainly) and sustainability assessment that will be available in the PARC model network developed in Task 8.3. This is of particular importance, since SSbD assessment at various stages of innovation requires the employment of tools of various complexity, that will be available through the modular design of the PARC model network.

30) Readiness of ML and AI QSAR NAMs for chemicals NGRA

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 54

In collaboration with the PARC project P6.4.2.c-NAMAM ML and AI QSAR NAMs models that possibly result from the case studies will be contributed to the set of Integrative models.

31) Linking MCRA, Integra and PBK models

WR-BIOM and AUTH have started to develop an exchange system for dietary and non-dietary exposure data produced by one model and to be used by another model (see example in 5.3). The data transfer should include modelled uncertainty. For aggregation across various routes of exposure, it will also be needed to link with PBK models such as those developed in, e.g., task 6.2.2 and task 7.3.2.

5.5 Critical analysis of the situation

Critical analysis of the current state of development of the PARC risk modelling network, has identified the following two key points:

- Current progress of work with regard to the PARC model network is more than satisfactory. This includes:
 - The development of the conceptual model
 - Two concurrent strategies of development. i.e. the top-down and the bottom-up
 - Links to several case studies where experience will be gained and translated into refinement guidance
 - The inventory of the models available to PARC across the risk assessment continuum has been completed
- From the available model analysis, it has been made clear that there are several models that cover the initial part of the impact pathway. This pertains to models primarily relevant to environmental fate and exposure; as we move to the more biological interaction side, modelling and data related gaps are significant. More in detail, with regard to models for internal dosimetry, there are significant efforts towards the development of generic PBPK models, however, there are still needs for expanding the model parameterisation to cover a large chemical space. By moving further down the impact pathway, models for systems biology and assimilation for NAMs data towards pathway-based approaches are lacking, and this should be a priority for development in PARC and more particularly in WP8.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 55

6 Next steps towards model network implementation

6.1 General plan for operationalisation

Next steps towards implementation of the PARC integrative model network will focus on 1) further identification of user requirements, models and model links, 2) further elaboration of the overarching conceptual and technical design (top-down), and 3) linking of models in the context of specific needs and user requirements following from (PARC) case studies (bottom-up). The next deliverable (Month 24) will describe the progress made in developing the PARC integrative model network in the context of first applications of the network in practical use cases.

6.2 Further identification of user requirements

Further identification of the user requirements for the PARC integrative model network will be carried out amongst stakeholders, coming from the outcomes of respective workshops of potential users. The integrative network will also be disseminated to regulatory authorities which will also provide the user requirement needs. These workshops will be done in an annual basis, to incorporate their needs during the model development. The inventory of models and model links will be detailed further, also by considering additional models from inventories established in other PARC projects (e.g., aggregate exposure 6.2.1) and model information that is collected for each project in the data management plan (WP7).

6.3 Further elaboration of the overarching conceptual and technical design (top-down)

The model network will be expanded in a top-down and bottom-up fashion as detailed in section 4. Towards this end Task 8.3 representatives will continue to participate in cross-WP groups on structuring concepts, vocabularies, and semantic modelling. These activities will lead to a conceptual model for the PARC model and data landscape. From this it is expected that in time a PARC metamodel to describe all relevant entities for the risk assessment of chemicals will follow. In this context, a select number of existing frameworks inside and outside of PARC such as the modular design of INTEGRA and MCRA as well as initiatives such as [RAKIP-Web Model Repository](#), [EOSC Life](#), [OpenRiskNet](#), [FNS Cloud](#), [US EPA CompTox Dashboard](#) or [NICEATM Integrated Chemical Environment](#) will be considered.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 56

A main objective of the model network is early acceptance and to welcome early adopters/users as well as decision makers and regulators. This will be accomplished by considering two separate layers for model integration in the top-down approach, namely a transport layer and an application layer. The transport layer will focus on how different modelling tools can technically be connected in a workflow while the application layer will focus on semantic coupling of models. The transport layer of the model network will be agnostic to what it transports, and the aim is to keep the intelligence (software implementation and maintenance) as lean as possible. In a case study between AUTH and WR-BIOM a first demonstration of these concepts will be provided in the context of linking models of the INTEGRA and MCRA model toolboxes.

6.4 Linking of models in the context of specific needs and user requirements following from (PARC) case studies (bottom-up)

The bottom-up approach will focus on developing the model network in the context of practical use cases where there is a (regulatory) need to integrate models. Here, conceptual links will be established between specific models and a mapping of data formats will be carried out, especially having in mind assessments of aggregate exposure, PBK modelling, the use of HBM data in risk assessment and more specifically exposure reconstruction of HBM data. Case studies implemented in the Task 8.3, in collaboration with other projects and activities in PARC, will demonstrate how data across the source to dose and effect continuum are interconnected in both directions (from source to effect and vice versa).

To summarize, in year two of PARC, development of the model network will focus on:

- General: Refinement and implementation of the top-down/bottom-up strategy for establishing the model network.
- Conceptual: (a) Specification of sub-domains in the PARC model network, e.g., PBK models, aggregate exposure modelling, analysis of HBM data, etc., and (b) for selected sub-domains, conceptual frameworks will be established to support harmonization of modelling tools
- Technical: (a) Refinement of model inventory, also focussing on technical aspects of the modelling tools, (b) review of other (previous and current) initiatives in which e-infrastructures were/are being created, specifically related to the life sciences, (c) explore the technical solutions for creating maintainable/sustainable (workflow-)infrastructures (also based on the review of other initiatives) leading to recommendations and a proposal for further development beyond Y2, and (c)

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 57

specific activities will be started on specific sub-domains of the PARC model network, following the bottom-up approach.

- Case studies: Implementation of model links in the context of the identified sub-domains, with a focus on modelling of internal human exposure to chemicals with the use of PBK models, establishing the link (forward and reverse) with measured HBM data, and subsequent (mixture) risk assessment.

A more refined roadmap for establishing the model network in PARC years three to seven will much depend on the findings and experiences of the activities in year two. In general terms, the activities beyond year 2 will focus on (a) further refinement of the overall conceptual framework, including alignment with WP7, (b) further refinement of the technical framework for implementation of modelling links and workflows and development of guidance thereof, (c) refinement of harmonisation and model interoperability for the sub-domains in scope of year 2, (d) inclusion of other domains focussing on risk assessment using new approach methodologies (e.g., NAMs, AOPs), (d) further implementation of model links and workflows in the context of specific case studies and testing and validation of the workflows against the regulatory requirements, and (e) development of an online resource of the PARC model network, including a catalogue of modelling tools, a catalogue of workflows, and access to dedicated user interface(s) for using these workflows.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 58

7 PARC model network exit strategy

PARC model network, aims at developing models and innovative concepts for risk assessment and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, facilitating integrated exposure, hazard, risk and (health) impact assessment of chemical substances by regulators, academic and industrial stakeholders. Given the importance of PARC model network in terms of supporting new generation risk assessment and its wealth of modelling capacities to be provided, it is important to ensure its sustainability after the end of the PARC project. Towards this aim, an exit strategy is necessary. Although this will be an evolving process continuously adapted to the current chemical risk assessment and available financing instruments landscape, the following points have to be considered:

7.1 Exit strategy timeline

- 3 Years before the end of PARC — At this point, the key elements of the exit strategy should be finalised, barring any major changes to the chemical risk assessment field. In this sense, we will identify the preferred exit path and to make the necessary operational changes to maximize the PARC model network valuation.
- 1 Year before the end of PARC - Concrete steps to implement the strategy such as interviewing potential users, creating legal documents, and identifying the framework to ensure maintenance and continuity. Sources for founding are identified very actively.
- 6 Months Out - Key management succession plans are put in place. Participation in new research, innovation, or demonstration actions are ensured.
- 12 Months Out - The PARC model network is further promoted to prospective user communities. Management responsibilities are re-evaluated but not necessarily transitioned. Key users are informed about the new status.

7.2 Evaluate the factors that impact an exit

- Exit goals: Clear identification of the exit strategy; this is to maintain the PARC model network as the most comprehensive modelling ecosystem for chemical risk assessment.
- Heavy reliance on the developer skills, relationships and oversight: It is important that PARC model network will ensure proper maintenance and update, even if key experts might go in pension or they are not further involved in the PARC modelling network development after the end of the PARC project.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 59

- Acquiring financing: Identification of competitive EU projects and successful participation of the PARC model network managers is essential.
- Identifying the right successor: Internal management or eventually developing a management team that will have the responsibility for the PARC model network legacy is important, eventually development of a spin-off.
- Maintaining continuity: Exits often result in churn of customers and employees who were loyal to the previous owner. Communicating the transition and retaining top talent throughout the process is critical.
- Transition planning: What is the detailed plan to transfer relationships and knowledge to new managerial scheme over a 3 month period?
- Communication strategy: How will the transition be announced and explained to internal and external stakeholders?

Having clarity across these dimensions will lead to an exit strategy tailored to the PARC modelling network situation and goals. Proactively developing strategies to mitigate these risks within the next years of the PARC duration will place tech service owners in a much better position when exploring exit options.

7.3 Increase online presence and PPARC model network awareness

The key is working early enough to implement strategies and demonstrate results before the end of the PARC project. Strategies towards this aim, include:

- Expand further the online presence - Get the website ranking higher in search engines, create engaging social media content, etc. This will makes the appear larger and more established to potential buyers.
- Improve content - Optimize PARC model network website and online content for keywords and search engines, while further enhancing the link with PARCopedia. This can drive more traffic to the site, making the PARC model network seem more valuable.
- Collect visitors and user data and analytics - Demonstrate the growth and potential of PARC model network by collecting user data.
- With an expanded digital presence, brand name, and data-driven growth, PARC model network becomes more attractive as a key partner for future proposals. This will put the PARC model network in a stronger negotiating position to ask for a higher budget share.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 60

7.4 Communicate the exit strategy to developers, users, and stakeholders

A clear communication plan helps retain key staff and customers through the uncertainty of a transition:

- Developers and contributors of the PARC model network should be told early on and reassured about opportunities after the PARC project ends.
- Users and stakeholders require plenty of notice about continuity ensured through the transition and introduction to new points of contact (if needed) to maintain trust.
- Promotion strategies can help frame the news as a positive transition.
- External stakeholders may need to be notified depending on contractual obligations.
- Transparency and frequent status updates reduce confusion around changes occurring during an exit.

7.5 Identify the legal and financial considerations during the exit process

Key legal and financial considerations will have to be considered during the exit of the PARC project including:

- Projecting potential costs necessary for the maintenance should be ensured for the transition period.
- Further develop the financing development post-exit.
- Clearly define the management and the potential ownership scheme.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 61

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D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 62

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D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 63

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D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 64

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D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 65

9 Annex: Models available within the PARC consortium to be included in the network

9.1 Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) toolbox

Here we update a description of the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) toolbox as provided previously as deliverable of the EuroMix project (van der Voet et al. 2020). The MCRA toolbox for mixture risk assessment has been built according to the modular design shown in Figure A1. The modules are of three basic types: 1. Scoping modules regarding primary entities on which the risk assessment is built; 2. Data modules, specifying groups of data sources needed or optional for the assessment; and 3. Calculator modules, which calculate results of a certain type. Note, that calculator modules can in principle also act as data modules if the results are already available from previous work. This has been implemented partially in the current state.

Figure A1. Modular design of the MCRA toolbox. Not all links are shown in this graph.

The primary entities in the toolbox relate to the agents of risk (Substances), the sources of dietary exposure (Foods), the objects of protection (Populations), the potential hazards (Effects), and how these are measured (Responses in Test systems). The data

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 66

and calculation modules on the left side of Figure 1 are related to exposure assessment, those on the right side to hazard identification and hazard characterisation. The module for risk assessment is in the middle of the diagram, integrating exposures and hazard characterisations.

The exposures module can aggregate non-dietary exposures (which then need to be provided as data) and dietary exposures. Dietary exposures are calculated from consumptions and concentrations, possibly incorporating many detailed aspects. Food consumptions may need to be redefined by conversion of food codes from the codes used in consumption surveys to the codes used in concentration monitoring data. Occurrence data (concentrations and substance authorisations) may need to be converted due to differences between active substances and measured substances (in the pesticide field known as complex residue definitions), and such data may be condensed in concentration models (e.g. a lognormal distribution with a spike of non-detects). Total diet study (TDS) concentration data require a conversion to appropriate food codes. Exposures may also be adjusted for food processing effects and for the greater concentration variability in units of consumption compared to the composite samples used in the monitoring program. In addition, modelled exposures may be inspected for co-occurrence of substance combinations as exposure mixtures, and they may be compared to human monitoring data.

Hazard identification is concerned with identifying the active substances related to a given health effect. AOP networks may be used to identify relevant effects connected to the adverse outcome of interest in the assessment. Identification of active substances as belonging to the relevant assessment groups (AG) may be just specified as data, or it may be derived from available toxicity data or from in silico models (QSAR and/or molecular docking). Effect representations data will link observed responses to effects of interest and may specify benchmark responses, which are toxicologically relevant levels for those responses, to be used in the modelling of dose-response data to obtain benchmark doses (BMDs). BMDs as well as other points of departure (POD) specified as data can then be used for hazard characterisation, either directly or after applying assessment factors for POD type, species differences and/or within-species variability. Kinetic models (or simple absorption factors) may be used to extrapolate between external and internal doses. We use the term hazard characterisation (HC) as a generic term which can be any form of POD or health-based guidance value, depending on the purpose of the analysis. For the assessment of mixtures, RPFs are calculated as the ratio of HC for an index substance to HC for a specific substance.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 67

The toolbox distinguishes between two types of runs: the nominal run and the uncertainty analysis loop. The nominal run represents a single calculation in which the aim is to compute the most likely, if possible unbiased estimates for the model at hand. E.g., when computing dietary exposure distributions, the nominal run computes one exposure distribution, using, as much as possible, fixed values for all uncertain inputs, and summarises the exposure distribution by point estimates of statistics such as the mean exposure or specific percentiles of variability. In the uncertainty analysis, on the other hand, the calculation run is repeated a number of times, each time with a different uncertainty scenario obtained using bootstrapping, parametric resampling, and/or re-calculation of uncertain values, yielding uncertainty distributions and confidence intervals for specific outputs. Making the distinction between the nominal run and the uncertainty loops has the practical advantage that it allows the user to setup and evaluate complex simulations first using only the nominal runs to quickly obtain a picture of the results and identify possible errors in the data or in the model settings before running the more time-consuming uncertainty analysis loop.

User work is organized in workspaces. A workspace is a collection of work items that are logically grouped together. A workspace has a name, description and, optionally, a number of tags. Users are the owners of their own workspace folders. An action is started with the module of the corresponding action type (e.g. dietary exposures), but also links to other modules that are needed for its completion (e.g. consumptions per food as measured, consumptions, foods, etc.). An action can be available in two forms: 1) a data selection action and 2) a calculation action. A data selection action comprises the selection of already available data of that action type, optionally the specification of selections on that data, and in some cases some pre-processing of data. A calculation action is an action in which the data of that action is calculated based on relevant input and specific calculator settings. Within a workspace, multiple actions can be created. When running an action, a task is spawned that produces output. Output is available in the form of reports or in the form of data that can be used as input in other actions. Actions have multiple outputs when settings are changed. Output reports are presented as screen reports or print reports and structured according to the modules of the modular design.

The MCRA toolbox contains a repository for relevant data. Data can be uploaded by individual users or by representatives of a larger user group. Data can be shared with other users or user groups. The data administrator for each data set can decide on use, read, or read/write permission for users. The data collected during the EuroMix project (Data/EuroMix repository) are shared with project participants and other stakeholders

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 68

and are summarised in Table 5. These data collected in the EuroMix project were the basis for the examples shown below.

Table 5. Data in the MCRA toolbox, as collected in the EuroMix project. For specific data regarding modules that were not in the focus of the EuroMix project and therefore not included in this table, references are van Klaveren et al. (2019ab) for Unit variability factors, Substance authorisations, Substance conversions, Concentration limits and Food extrapolations, Kolbaum et al. (2019) for TDS sample compositions, van der Voet et al. (2009) for Intra-species factors and Inter-species factors.

Module	Description data sets
Foods	2289 foods-as-eaten and foods-as-measured coded in FoodEx1 (EFSA, 2011) 32 processing types
Substances	1629 substances, classified in categories PPPs, Biocides, Alkaloids, EnvironmentalPollutants, FoodAdditives, Mycotoxins (Kyriakopoulou et al., 2017)
Effects AOP networks	48 effects in 7 AOP networks related to liver steatosis, reproductive toxicity and craniofacial malformations
Populations	15 population groups from 10 countries (different age groups) (Crépet et al., 2019a)
Test systems Responses Effect representations	14 test systems, 477 responses, 162 effect representations (Luckert et al., 2019; Schreiber et al., 2019ab)
Consumptions	11 files with food consumption data in 10 countries (Crépet et al., 2019a)
Food recipes	5555 records specifying food ingredients in the FoodEx1 system or conversions (Boon et al., 2015)
Concentrations	Food monitoring data 2010-2014, SSD formatted data (Crépet et al., 2019a)
Processing factors	667 processing factors for pesticides and environmental pollutants (derived from Verarbeitungs-faktoren_3-0.xls, downloaded 01-09-2015 from https://www.bfr.bund.de/de/a-z_index/verarbeitungs-faktoren-8400.html)
Non-dietary exposures	Simulated non-dietary exposures from Browse and Bream2 (Kennedy et al., 2019)
Human monitoring data	Norwegian biomonitoring study (Husøy et al., 2019)
QSAR membership models	26 QSAR models applied to all substances in the EuroMix chemical inventory (Rorije et al., 2019)
Molecular docking models	20 Molecular docking models applied to all substances in the inventory (Rorije et al., 2019)
Kinetic models	EuroMix Generic PBTK model parametrised for 9 substances based on htk and for all substances in the inventory based on QSAR (Tebby et al., 2019)

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 69

Module	Description data sets
Points of departure	144 NOAEL or LOAEL values related to Steatosis-liver (Crépet et al., 2019a); PODs for oral exposure for ~10,000 chemical substances for developmental/reproductive toxicity and for other non-cancer toxicity effects (Aurisano et al. 2023)
Dose response data	28 files describing experiments with single substances or mixtures , on 15 responses (or groups) in 9 test systems in 6 laboratories (Luckert et al., 2019, Schreiber et al., 2019ab)

9.2 INTEGRA

The objective of INTEGRA was to bring together all available information within a coherent methodological framework for assessing the source-to-dose continuum for the entire life cycle of substances covering an extensive chemical space. Hence, the major component of INTEGRA is a unified computational platform that integrates environmental fate, exposure and internal dose dynamically in time. In this way, the platform is able to differentiate between biomonitoring data corresponding to steady exposure patterns as opposed to acute, one-off exposures. A conceptual representation of the various elements involved in INTEGRA and the way they are lined is graphically illustrated in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Conceptual representation of INTEGRA

The platform has been largely validated using human biomonitoring data from Europe and the USA, for a variety of compounds covering a large chemical space. Aggregate

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 70

exposure assessment is data-intensive, requiring detailed information at every step of the source-to-dose pathway. To accommodate these needs, the INTEGRA modelling framework (Sarigiannis et al., 2014) aims at bringing together all available information for assessing the source-to-dose continuum for the entire life cycle of substances covering an extensive chemical space. The major component of INTEGRA is an integrative computational platform that comprises environmental fate, exposure and internal dose dynamically in time using a Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) probabilistic analysis framework. The INTEGRA platform includes the following components:

1. Multimedia model to account for multi-scale (far field exposure) interactions affecting the environmental transport and fate of chemicals: The multimedia environmental modelling framework for INTEGRA, follows the ECHA guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment (ECHA, 2012). All different spatial scales (local, regional, continental and global), media exchange (air, soil, water, sediment and transfer to food items such as crops, meat, milk and fish) and environmental processes (emissions, advection, diffusion, and degradation) used in EUSES (Lijzen, 2004) were taken into account.
2. Indoor micro-environmental modelling and detailed personal exposure assessment (near field exposure): In terms of indoor microenvironments, a two-zone model was developed (Sarigiannis et al., 2012b), also accounting for partitioning among gaseous, particles and settled dust phase (Sarigiannis et al., 2012a). Exposure is explicitly described for each pathway and route of exposure, taking into account all the age and gender exposure modifiers, such as activity based inhalation rate, dietary patterns and intake rates per food item, amount of soil and dust ingested or hand-to-mouth behaviour.
3. A generic PBTK model that captures satisfactorily life stage changes and physiological and metabolic efficiency change over an individual's lifetime (from conception till 80 years of age): The generic PBTK model developed in INTEGRA is designed to describe in as much as possible detail the ADME processes occurring in the human body at different life stages, to be easily applicable to a broad variety of chemicals after proper parameterization. The model in its generic form includes the parent compound and up to three generations of potential metabolites (Sarigiannis et al., 2014). Advanced QSAR models are used to estimate physicochemical and biochemical parameters of the model to expand its applicability domain to a large chemical space. All major human organs are included, as well as arterial, venous, and portal blood compartments. Xenobiotics and their metabolites are linked through the

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 71

metabolizing tissues. This is mainly the liver, but also other sites of metabolism might be considered (intestine, brain, skin, placenta) based on the presence or not of the enzymes involved in the metabolism of the compound of interest. The mass balance equation for each compartment describes all appropriate parameters carrying biological significance, such as absorption, metabolism, elimination, and protein binding. In practice, in each tissue three mass balance equations are written, for (a) red blood cells, (b) plasma and interstitial tissue and (c) cells, allowing the application of the model to both flow limited, as well as membrane-limited compounds. Specific organs were further divided in sub-compartments: liver is divided in up to 5 compartments to better describe the distribution of enzymes, and brain is divided in four sub-compartments, namely, main brain, globus palidus, cerebellum and pituitary, so as to better describe the permeability differences among the different brain regions. The model describes mother fetus interactions by modelling the intra-placental properties that govern the transfer of xenobiotics and their metabolites from the mother to the fetus as it grows. The anthropometric parameters of the models are time dependent, to provide a lifetime internal dose assessment, as well as to describe the continuously changing physiology of the mother and the developing fetus. The model include the diffusion flow from uterus to placenta and vice-versa during pregnancy (Beaudouin et al., 2010). Excretion via lactation is described as an output from the mammary tissue compartment through a partitioning process between mammary tissue and milk, and milk withdrawal by suckling, as described for PCBs in rats (Lee et al., 2007) and further adopted for humans (Verner et al., 2008). The model also includes a detailed description for the three main routes of exposure. Inhalation considers absorption of gases and deposition fractions of particles across the different human respiratory tract regions based on particles size distribution. Absorption through the oral route is governed by the absorption rates of stomach and intestine. To better describe dermal absorption, skin has been modeled as a two layer structure, including stratum corneum that has been described as a “bricks and mortar” structure (Touitou, 2002) and viable epidermis (also accounting for metabolism), where the geometry of all layer microstructure has been explicitly described (Mitragotri et al., 2011).

4. *Inverse modelling module for exposure reconstruction and human biomonitoring (HBM) data assimilation:* The PBTK model is geared with reverse modeling algorithms to reconstruct exposure from human biomonitoring (HBM) data. Assimilation of human biomonitoring data and their translation into intake distribution amounts to a computational inversion problem, where the objective is to identify the specific input distributions that best explain the observed outputs while minimizing the residual error.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 72

Inputs involve spatial and temporal information on micro-environmental media concentrations of xenobiotics and corresponding information on human activities, food intake patterns or consumer product use that result in intakes; outputs are the observed biomonitoring levels.

More in detail, a computational framework was developed based on Bayesian Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) combined with the generic Physiological Based Pharmacokinetic (PBBK) model aiming at performing accurate exposure reconstruction. Differential Evolution (DE) and MCMC algorithms have been combined to this problem for the first time. The PBBK model has been combined with the Bayesian MCMC (Gilks and Roberts, 1996, Haario et al., 2006) and DEMC (Ter Braak, 2006) techniques in order to simulate and calculate the exposure value that fits best the observed HBM data. The conceptual framework for exposure reconstruction of the process described above is graphically illustrated in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Exposure reconstruction conceptual framework

9.3 VEGAHUB

VEGAHUB includes several collections of tools. Some tools can be used by experts to develop new models. This is the case of the tools such as CORAL, SARpy, QSARpy, aiQSAR.

There are about 100 QSAR models prebuilt, the VEGA models, to be used to get predictions for properties which are:

- Toxicological
- Ecotoxicological

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 73

- Environmental
- Physico-chemical
- Toxicokinetic.

In several cases there is more than one model for the same endpoint.

These QSAR models provide the prediction, the experimental value (if present in the set of substances used to build up the model), the most similar substances (and thus the same tool can be used for read-across), the information on the presence of structural alerts related to the effect, the applicability domain measured in a quantitative way. The uncertainty of the prediction is provided, based on the separate software which measures the applicability domain value. It has been demonstrated that the predictions showing higher applicability domain value are more reliable.

These QSAR models have been developed using different algorithms and molecular descriptors. Some models are taken from other platforms, such as TEST, OPERA, Toxtree, EPISuite. The advantage of using these models in VEGA is the possibility to measure the applicability domain and visualize the most similar substances.

The VEGA models are documented, and the QMRF are available from the website. The documentation also regards the availability of the datasets used to build up the model, and the user guide.

The VEGA models are also at the basis of other software systems available in VEGAHUB. JANUS combines 48 different models to prioritize substances for PBT, CMR and endocrine disruption. JANUS processes the parental compound and generate environmental degradation products, which are processed as well.

The VEGA models are also used within VERMEER. The VERMEER model for cosmetics is fully implemented with VEGA models. The other VERMEER models integrate the VEGA models with the MERLIN-Expo platform for exposure. In the case of food contact materials, the migration from the food container into the food is predicted. The hazard associated to these contaminants is then evaluated with the VEGA models.

The ToxEraser model for cosmetics evaluates safer ingredients. The functional use is also evaluated based on the categories of cosmetics, organized into many categories in a hierarchical way.

9.4 STACKn

STACKn is a lightweight, cloud-native machine learning platform that lets data scientist collaborate on ML projects where they can share datasets, work in Notebook environments, track experiments and serve ML models. STACKn also lets you deploy models and apps in public or private catalogues for sharing model endpoints and

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 74

custom dashboards. Within PARC, STACKn will be used as a general platform for deploying and serving AI models. STACKn is open source (<https://github.com/scaleoutsystems/stackn>) and backed by Scaleout Systems. It runs on Kubernetes and can serve in principle all containerized services.

The majority of currently available models are for drug/chemical safety and trained using the CPSign modeling software (<https://github.com/arosbio/cpsign>). The most well-equipped instance of STACKn is operated by SciLifeLab and branded as SciLifeLab Serve (<https://serve.scilifelab.se/>). The majority of currently available models are for drug/chemical safety and trained using the CPSign modeling software (<https://github.com/arosbio/cpsign>).

9.5 QsarDB

The QsarDB repository (<https://qsardb.org>, (Ruusmann et al., 2015)) is an open access data repository and has been operating at University of Tartu since 2012. The repository follows FAIR principles for scientific data and model management. All data submissions are characterized with extensive metadata and are linked with the original publications. The repository assigns Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) which makes it suitable as a platform for data publications.

The QsarDB repository includes a large collection of QsarDB archives that contain one or more QSAR/QSPR models. Currently 227 QsarDB archives with more than 500 QSAR/QSPR models are stored in the repository. The majority of these archives originate from scientific publications and currently models from 187 papers have been published. Generally, the usability of models from scientific literature is difficult (Piir et al., 2018). In addition, some models originate from community projects (e.g. Open Notebook Science). Models can be supplemented with QMRF documents and the repository also accepts the submission of only QMRF documents for documenting QSAR models available elsewhere. Currently the repository includes 75 QMRF documents describing models.

Models in the repository have been developed by different research groups and cover a wide variety of endpoints and physicochemical properties. For many endpoints more than one model is available, where different training sets and modeling approaches have been used.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 75

The modeled endpoints can be divided to the following six groups:

1. Physical Chemical Properties
2. Environmental fate parameters
3. Ecotoxic effects
4. Human health effects
5. Toxicokinetics
6. Other

The QsarDB archive is an open data format (Ruusmann et al., 2014) for organizing and storing QSAR/QSPR models and related data in a transparent way. Each model is represented in machine readable format. The repository defaults to predictive model markup language (PMML), but the system is open for extending with other open data formats. A wide range of regression and classification model types can be stored in the repository, both classical statistical and advanced machine learning approaches. For example, the repository includes linear regression (MLR), decision trees (DT), logistic regression, k-nearest neighbor (k-NN), random forest (RF), support vector machine (SVM), artificial neural network (ANN), etc. models. In addition, training and validation sets for the models are included together with structural, property and descriptor data.

The repository provides advanced web-based user interface for exploring and visualization of the models (e.g. scatter plots and histograms for property and descriptor data, applicability domain characterization with Williams and Insubria plots). The models can be used for predictions via web application or REST service. Since all models are machine readable, they can be used for predictions when descriptor values provided by the user. In addition, description calculation is supported for models that have been developed with descriptors that can be calculated with open-source software. The uncertainty of predictions is characterized with applicability domain analysis, which includes the evaluation of descriptor, structural and response domains. In addition, the prediction is complemented with the list of most similar chemicals in the training set of the model. The prediction result from QsarDB can be saved in a partially filled QPRF (QSAR Prediction Reporting Format) document containing relevant information about the prediction.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 76

9.6 Specific PBK, systems biology model and AOPbot

IISPV has specific PBPK model available for compounds like PFAS, Bisphenols, phthalates, flame retardants etc. with focus on both forward and reverse dosimetry. The advanced QSAR models have been attached to PBPK for finding unknown parameters like partition coefficient using multiple methods (Rodgers and Rowland, Schmitt, PK-Sim, and Poulin and Theil). The model codes are available in R, MCSIM with R and Berkley Madonna. The PBPK model developed in our lab is perfusion-limited for most chemicals but we also have option to extend to permeability-limited model. For long-acting compounds like PFAS, we have life stage model with renal transporters to focus on aspects like accumulation of compound in different organ, and varied half-life with age for risk assessment (Deepika et al., 2021). The model developed for Bisphenol A considers gender-specific differences. For compounds like bisphenol A and its analogues, we have special model including complex metabolism aspects like Phase II metabolism (Deepika et al., 2022). Our models are compound-specific, for instance for compounds like organophosphate flame retardant, we have extensive enterohepatic recirculation to account for fecal excretion (Deepika et al. 2023, unpublished). IISPV also have specialized models like Pregnancy PBPK model which take into account varied physiology and anatomy of pregnant female along with ADME profile in fetus to evaluate fetal risk (Sharma et al., 2018, Rovira et al., 2019). In recent years, the specific PBPK has been extended to account for organ-specific risk. We have developed a brain specific PBPK model for compounds like PFOS and PFOA to evaluate the kinetic changes in hippocampus, cerebrospinal fluid, and cortex regions for predicting neurotoxicity.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Krusselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 77

Figure 11: Multi-compartment PBPK model with 12 compartments. Excretion of the compound is from feces via gut, urine via kidney and breath via lung respectively (Deepika and Kumar 2023)¹.

Figure 12: Integrating in-vitro data in PBPK to build brain-specific PBPK for neurotoxicity (Figure adapted from unpublished article).

¹ Deepika, D.; Kumar, V. The Role of “Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic Model (PBPK)” New Approach Methodology (NAM) in Pharmaceuticals and Environmental Chemical Risk Assessment. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 2023, 20, 3473. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20043473>

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 78

All the models have fast processing time (within minutes) due to integration with MCSIM. Uncertainty for biochemical parameters is incorporated in the model with flexibility of providing normal with SD, log normal and many other types of distribution. Virtual population can be created in the model with varied physiological parameters to incorporate variability in the PBPK. All the specific models provides flexibility to conduct reverse dosimetry for reconstructed exposure utilizing Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulation. Option has been provided for user to run multiple independent parallel chains for reaching convergence after MCMC simulation. All the models have been automated to read the data from excel file and conduct fast individual simulation (within hours) for thousands of data points considering individual parameters like body weight, height, gestational age etc. to account for variability. Recently the model has been converted to interactive web app through Rshiny with the option to host it on cloud if required.

Systems Biology Model

IISPV has systems biology model for oxidative stress focusing on ROS network describing ROS management through multiple positive and negative feedback loops (N. Kolodkin et al., 2020). Model includes various scenarios like antioxidant response and mitoptosis, Keap1-NRF2 module with negative feedback, mitochondrial repair via NF-KB signalling, DJ-1 as ROS sensor, variable levels of healthy mitochondria and ROS among others. The model is validated for aging, and neurotoxicity with special focus on memory impairment and Parkinson disease. Overall model has 63 substances, 61 reactions and more than 100 parameters values. Model network was generated using cell designer, transferred to COPASI, a systems biology markup language and later extended in R standalone, and MCSIM with R. The ROS model has been integrated with brain PBPK to account for kinetic and dynamic changes happening inside brain. This model can be easily extended to liver- and immunotoxicity. The ROS model is open access and available on FAIRDOM hub.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Krusselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 79

Figure 13: Network diagram for ROS management (A systems biology model).

IISPV is leading Task 7.3.3 for the development of text mining tools. Developed Text mining tool aims in gathering literature-based evidence from sources and merge it with the previously available pathway and biological information. This tool provides the platform to the researcher to gather and store evidence of their experimental studies as well. In the development process of the tools, exhaustive literature search has been done to list the best available method to be used for development. State of the art NLP (Natural Language processing) architecture such as BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representation from Transformer) and GPT (Generative pre-trained Transformers) are being used to evidence extraction. Large language model (LLM) trained on biological corpora, such as PubMed and PMC (PubMed central) are used, to understand the scientific context of literature. Development of this tools has is being done in rational way, specific component will be developed by expertise.

Figure 14: Proposed architecture of Text mining tool for AOP development.

D8.3: Conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network	Dissemination level: P
WP8: Concepts and toolboxes	Version: 4
Main Authors: Denis Sarigiannis, Spyros Karakitsios, Jasper Engel, Johannes Kruisselbrink, Hilko van der Voet	Page: 80

Components such as Entity normalizer, Entities Extractor, Relation Extractor are core, which is crucial for given reliable downstream performance. Apart from that database such as CTD, HIPPIE, PID, Geneways, DisGeNet etc. will be merged for information enrichment. Continuous development method has been adopted. This tool will be open-source for further development.